

CALIFORNIA'S FUTURE ECONOMIC COLLAPSE DUE TO A DECREASE OF QUALITY OF LIFE
IN THE HISPANIC/LATINX FIELDWORKER POPULATION OF THE CENTRAL VALLEY

by

Sonny A. Bianchi I

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Approved by:

Dr. Alexandro Gradilla, Department of Chicano/a Studies

Dr. Stacy Mallicoat, Director, University Honors Program

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5/19/23

THE CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, FULLERTON
UNIVERSITY HONORS PROGRAM STATEMENT OF
COMMITTEE APPROVAL

Dr. Stacy Mallicoat, Director

Department of University Honors Program

Dr. Alejandro J. Gradilla, Associate Professor

Department of Chicana and Chicano Studies

Dr. Christopher W. Gibson, Associate Professor

Department of Sociology

Approved by:

Dr. Yuying Tsong, Former Director, University Honors Program

Dedicated to:

The love of my life, Darsey Roque Morales. The place that encouraged me to achieve everything that I set my mind to, the Central Valley. The friends, mentors, and professors who have encouraged me on this four year journey.

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ABSTRACT

The Latinx/Hispanic fieldworkers within the Central Valley (CV) of California continue to create economic growth within the agriculture industry in California and the United States. Because of the economic development of this state, this population's quality of life (QOL) is decreasing, leading to the state's economic collapse if health inequalities are not addressed. The dominant explanation for this trend is a lack of policy development and Eurocentric ideas within the agricultural industry. Previous research has primarily relied on the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) trends to relate to life satisfaction; thus, research does not address a culturally competent understanding/issues within QOL based on GDP growth. Using a survey, a collection of responses was recorded to calculate further the QOL index for the Latinx/Hispanic fieldworkers' population within the CV. Using the QOL index calculated for this population, the Cultural Health Analysis Theory will be used to analyze the index to establish the relationship between the QOL and GDP. The Cultural Health Analysis Theory shows a negative correlation between the QOL for Latinx/Hispanic fieldworkers and GDP growth. Furthermore, our results show that if the QOL does not improve, California's economy will collapse, and the state will fall into a worse recession.

INTRODUCTION

The Central Valley (CV) is a region of California expanding from the Shasta Cascade down to the Tehachapi Mountain Ranges, and averages fifty miles in width (see Figure 1 below). Within the CV there are over seven million people who reside within this region, mostly due to migration, but also for jobs, housing, and family costs (America Counts Staff, 2021). While many expect that the Valley to be a majority of Latinx or Hispanic, the CV is a melting pot of culture where no one ethnic group is a majority. Because of this, the CV faces many issues that the rest of California does not see. The CV faces a large housing crisis, there is a pollution problem due to all the harmful chemical exposures, lack of worker regulation, contaminated water, and lack of medical accessibility (Newel, 2017). As a result of lack of resources and the unethical practices of farmers within this region, unregulated working practices for fieldworkers continue to happen. Therefore, contribution and growth to the Californian economy continues to happen.

Figure 1. Shows the breakdown of the mountain ranges of California. This figure also highlights the counties within the Central Valley of California. Placer County is a part of the Central Valley, but the Central Valley does not expand to the Eastern border.

Living in the CV one in five residents will find themselves living in poverty, meaning than an estimated 1.4 million people are facing poverty (Yen, 2020). Because of the high rates of poverty across each county, many of the residents of the CV must take on jobs that places extreme pressures on their lives. The CV is composed of a choice system and individuals who create the systems within the CV set out to preferentialize the rich at the expense of the poor. The political leaders of this system are willing to utilize racist policies to disembowel a community because of their skin color. As a result, the choice system that is found in the CV is comprised of elected officials chosen by big farmers. Candidates that are chosen by big farmers will receive funding and support, once the candidate wins. The candidate then works for the farmers and choose not to represent their constituents. This political system found within this region, currently makes land, water management, and policy decisions that creates short-term economic gains that jeopardize the land and community alike. This system is sufficient for big farmers who can sway policy but affects the quality of life for the rest of the residents of this region.

BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT

The birth of California happened in 1848 when the United States and Mexico government signed the Treaty of Guadalupe Hidalgo to officially end the Mexican-American War. It wasn't until 1850, after the Californian Gold Rush of 1849, which enticed people to come to this state for a better future and wealthy outcomes. With the growth of the northern city, San Francisco, as its hub; Northern California began to grow because of the potential of finding gold. Unlike Northern California, Southern California was rich in something else, oil (Heizer, 1940). While the two distinct parts of the "culture" of California began to grow and create an affective economy for the newly founded state, what was happening in the CV?

In 1862, under the Presidency of Abraham Lincoln, congress enacted the Pacific Railroad Act that was supposed to start in Sacramento and expand eastward to the Mississippi River. Congress then chartered different railroad companies giving the incentive of every three quarters of a mile, one quarter would go to the company in return for contributing to for formation of the railroad (Blackford, 1970). In 1866, the Southern Pacific acquired the San Francisco & San Jose Railroad following authorization by the state legislature in March. The Southern Pacific was purchased by the directors of the Central Pacific, Leland Stanford, Collins P. Huntington, Mark Hopkins, and Charles Crocker in September 1868. The Southern Pacific line was extended, with service operating to Delano in July 1873.

When the Southern Pacific Railroad, began planning a route through the Southern part of the state, both city and county leaders of Los Angeles realized that Los Angeles and its emerging port were dependent on a railroad. The railroad system was essential to linking the rest of the nation to Los Angeles to have any hope of survival in the future (Lowell, 1985). Southern Pacific partner Charles Crocker reminded city leaders of the consequences if they failed to cooperate, "I will make grass grow in your streets," (Bailey, 1908). Southern California and the East were linked later after the threats of farmer Crocker at Lang Station, near Palmdale on September 5, 1876. Because of the power of the railroad barons, the opening of the Southern Pacific line between Los Angeles and San Francisco became possible. Through the railroad system, accessibility to Northern California to Southern Californian made it possible for the CV to be established. As a direct result of the railroad system, the CV's agriculture industry began to increase at an exponential rate. Smaller cities and towns began to be founded around the CV and different sectors of the agricultural industry began to thrive. The sectors that became prosperous include cattle, fruits, vegetables, and even farming equipment industry (Purdum, 2000).

While the other two parts of California began to grow and solidify in their industry, so did the CV, through agriculture. When the First World War broke out, California played a pivotal role in producing food, finance, and propaganda. California was most successful in providing food for the Allies. As a result, the United States was most noted for giving food after the First World War (North, 2018). Most of the food that was supplied by the United States came from the CV. This established the CV's agricultural influence, economy, and control over labor policy. As a direct result of the establishment of the CV, the population to begin to grow in the CV. The state's population exploded from 380,000 in 1860 to almost 3.5 million in 1920, largely due to swelling immigration from other parts of the United States as well as Latin America, Asia, and Europe (Paddison, 2005). Pulled by dreams of economic success, as promised by state boosters, these migrants found both opportunity and hardship in modernizing California.

Even though that the CV began to grow; obstacles, such as the Great Depression in 1929 lasting until 1939, forced this region of California to develop and evolve. During the evolution of this region, the Dust Bowl broke out within the Midwest of the United States forcing many to abandon their homes and migrate westwards. Many of them came to California and settled within the CV. These people who migrated here were called "Okies," this is because most of these migrants came from Oklahoma. "Okies" were critical to the CV because this population was able to come and boost the economy by introducing more drought resistant agriculture. From the migration of "Okies" and their contribution to the evolution of this industry, the CV has remained a large part of the California economy (Worster, 1979).

California has a 235-year history within the sector of agriculture (Johnston & McCalla). Over the development of the United States agricultural sector, the focus of agricultural development across the world has been found in this one state, California. As the industry

continues to grow and develop within our present day. The agricultural industry is estimated to be a 55-billion-dollar industry and continues to spread its influence affecting the quality of life for Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers across the state (Economic Reserach Service, Farm finance indicators, state ranking, 2020, 2022). California's economic development in the agricultural industry is a direct result of the estimated million documented workers this industry employs annually (Martin, Hooker, Akhtar, & Stockton, 2016). With California only having 28% of the state in prime condition to be use for agricultural land; most of the state's land is used to for urbanization of cities (Thompson, Jr., 2009). The total land use of prime agriculture land in California is relative to the size of Denmark. Therefore, how does California have a such a strong hold over this industry?

The answer is north of the Tejon Mountain Ranges (see figure 2. below), where we find the heart of this industry, the CV. With a population of well over seven million people, the CV is the biggest contribution to the growth of this industry (America Counts Staff, 2021). Using fewer than 1% of the national farmland, the CV produces 8% of the national agricultural output annually (California's Central Valley, n.d.). Because of such a massive output of agricultural goods, the state of California employs an estimated work force of 500,000 to 800,000 field workers and 75% of these workers are to be undocumented (Lopez, 2014). As a result, 45% of all farmworkers live within five counties: Fresno, Monterey, Kern, Tulare, and Ventura (Mines, 2006). Three of these counties are located within the CV, contributing to the development of this industry over the past 235 years.

Figure 2. This map shows the location of the Tejon Mountain Range of California. The figure also shows the location of the Central Valley in relation to the different mountain ranges of California.

While the agriculture industry in the CV seems like there is positive feedback for the development of the infrastructure of this region of California, this isn't the case for all the residents in the area. The development of the agricultural industry is at the benefit of big farmers within the CV. In May 2008 within the vineyards of Merced County, the temperature hit 95 degrees Fahrenheit. Florentino Bautsta was working next to his fiancé, Maria Isabel Vasquez Jimenez (see figure 3.), when she collapsed. He describes the event as follows, "When she fell, she looked bad. She didn't regain consciousness. She just fell down and didn't react. I told her to be strong so we could see each other again," (ASSOCIATED PRESS, 2008). There was a water cooler ten minutes away, but Mr. Bautsta's boss would not allow him to take a break. After Maria had collapsed, farm management did not immediately take her to the hospital. Finally, by the time a doctor had treated her she was in a coma with a 108-degree fever. Two days later she passed away.

Figure 3. is a picture of Maria Isabel Vasquez Jimenez, an undocumented field worker, who died in this fatal event. This picture of Maria Isabel Vasquez Jimenez was accessible via NPR, Courtesy of Jocelyn Sherman of The United Farm Workers.

After this incident started to make headline news, authorities finally investigated the fateful event. In the report that the states of California's Division of Occupational Safety and Health pushed a report. The findings within this investigation decided that the Atwater-based farm company hired 17-year-old pregnant women, Maria, and the result of her death was caused by the denial of access to shade and water by her supervisor. They also found in this report that she was working for nine hours straight, and that the Atwater-based farm company failed to provide water and deliberately neglected to train workers and managers on how to stay safe while working in the Valley's punishing heat. The Atwater-based farm company was also found guilty of willing to ignore the state requirements for dealing with a medical emergency. This company faced a \$262,700 fine for violation of worker rights, unsafe labor practices, and willing to neglect state requirements for a medical emergency. The Merced Farm Labor also faced proceedings to revoke their license as a farmworker contractor by the California labor commission (Khokha, 2008).

The fateful incident of Maria Isabel Vasquez Jimenez highlights the issue of Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers within the CV. This event highlights the abuse of power that farmers and

farming commissions hold over their employees. This event explains how the development and practices are not enforced until it becomes a trending story within the media. Maria's story is one of the lucky ones that gets justice for the mistreatment of farm labor within the CV. This loss of life showcases the close association of Latinx and Hispanic ethnicity to working blue collar jobs in America. More in specific, the close relation of field work or construction to the Latinx and Hispanic culture. As a result, fieldworkers are at a higher risk for living in poverty, less likely to have health insurance, and lack the resources necessary to change their situation, at the expense of the unregulated practices of the agriculture industry (Weinstein, Geller, & Negussie, 2017). With the continued growth and development of agriculture in California's CV, it's surprising that every day thirteen people die each day within the agriculture industry (National Institute for Occupational Safety , 2021). This is a direct result of the economic hold the agriculture industry has on the United States, and its direct ties to policy. Subsequently, it's a result of the restrictive behaviors of the agricultural industry on the development of field worker population; blocking real labor reforms within the United States, and unregulated mandates for farmers to educate their hired labor on health issues that could arise while working in the fields.

The CV may seem very resilient and prosperous, but this is only the case for political figures and big farmers. Many in this region face working conditions that go unregulated, face homelessness, and human trafficking to survive. In some cases, residents of the CV are living in conditions where their town is run by gangs, and in other cities of this region residents do not have running water in their home. This region that supplies 8% of U.S. agricultural output (by value) and produces 1/4 of the nation's food, including 40% of the Nation's fruits, nuts, and other table fruit (Purdum, 2000), is deemed unimportant to many who do not realize where their food is coming from. A place where almost every single social justice issue can be found.

This region is an important part of-not only California's economy-but the entire United States. This region of California faces some of the highest rates of human trafficking rates, unregulated working conditions, homelessness, police brutality, domestic violence, drug use, high rates of high school to prison pipeline, insufficient healthcare systems, and a high teen pregnancy rate (Rosales, 2012). The CV is solely dependent on the agriculture industry's development. If we continue to allow the quality of life for Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers to decrease; then we are allowing an industry that spends \$5.9 billion on hired labor, \$3.4 billion on contracted labor and \$1.3 billion on custom labor (BENEFITS OF FARMLAND CONSERVATION IN CALIFORNIA , 2015), to destroy an economy that was built on the shoulders of Latinx and Hispanic fieldworker. If we want to keep this 55-billion-dollar industry from crashing down on itself, then the time to start improving the quality of life for Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers within the CV begins now.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

California's economy, as well as the United States economy, has seen an economic increase each year due the agriculture sector rapid increase and accounting for 1.6% of the country's GDP in 2013 (Medina, 2014). Even through the nation-wide pandemic of COVID-19, the labor force of the agriculture sector grew 1% and contributed to the economic growth of 5% (ERA Economics LLC, 2020). Using fewer than 1% of the United States farmland, the CV produces 8% of the United States agricultural output and creates an estimated \$17 billion in revenue, via crops (Purdum, 2000). As a result of California's agriculture sectors major contribution to the economy, many of its practices have gone unregulated within the CV, which has diminished the quality of life for many farmworkers within this region. Research on the relationship of farmworkers and the economy within the CV is limited. Through exploring

present peer reviewed research, consequences of the quality of life of farmworkers are decreasing because of the agricultural sectors rapid improvement/growth to the economy. Most present research is focused on the unregulated working practices and conditions that major farm companies have refused to comply, policy implementation failure by bureaucracies in the CV, and exposure of toxic material to field workers of this region.

Field workers' quality of life is decreasing because of the agriculture industry's unregulated practices and major contribution to the California and United States economy. If improvements to the quality of life for Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers do not improve, then the California economy will crash leading the United States into an economic disaster. Understanding why California's economy will crash because of the decline of quality of life for field workers in the CV; an in-depth qualitative and quantitative research is required to understand the relationship between the future economic collapse of California in relation to the decrease of quality of life for Latinx and Hispanic field workers within the CV.

When a specific group, like fieldworkers, have been overlooked and have become more excluded overtime, the possibilities of created political change through democratic institutions will continue to persist and become apparent to those within the community that is being overlooked. Focusing on fieldworkers' experiences within the fields of the CV can help develop more theories of ways to improve the quality of life for Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers in the CV to help prevent an economic elapse, as well as potentially informing future public policy and legislation. Addressing this problem will have practical benefits to the economy and to the quality of living for Latinx and Hispanic field workers in the CV, while also contributing to the wide spread of racial, societal, and structural issues that many face in this region of California.

This thesis aims to advocate and educate the rest of the nation about the working conditions and quality of life for Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers in the CV and through the rapid increase and development of California's agricultural sector and to the vast contribution on the economy has influenced these issues. A mixed methods approach will be used to gain and in-depth insight of the trials and tribulations of Latinx and Hispanic undocumented and documented fieldworkers of the CV, and how big farmers have contributed to the unethical treatment of fieldworkers. This data will be contextualized with review of recent peer reviewed literature on California's economy and issues presented to the Latinx and Hispanic community of fieldworkers within the CV.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Why is California deeply rooted within the agriculture industry, and how has this contributed to the economy? How has the rapid improvement of California's agricultural sectors to the economy, have affected the quality of life for Latinx and Hispanic field workers within the CV? What or how did the quality of life for Latinx and Hispanic field workers begin to decrease and continued to decrease? How have big farmers contributed to the decrease of quality of life for Latinx and Hispanic field workers within the CV? How has governmental agencies contributed to strengthening the power farmers have over Latinx and Hispanic field workers? How well developed is the CV's infrastructure to deal with the decrease health in the Latinx and Hispanic field workers? How might the economy be affected if the quality of life of field workers does not improve?

RELEVANCE AND IMPORTANCE OF THE RESEARCH

This research will provide a new perspective to relate the issues decreeing health in an ethnic community in relation to the growth of the economy. This study will also contribute to the

advancement of public health and economic awareness within the CV; by integrating policies and economic growth to the personal experiences of informants.

Specifically, the research is relevant to:

Communities- This study attempts to spread awareness to the farming community of the CV and even the state of California about the issues found within the agriculture industry of California. It also aims to recognize that the quality of life for all residents in the CV is at risk and tries to raise awareness that through possible political intervention and policy implementation we can try to improve the quality of health in this region.

Legislative Committees- This study provides context about the CV and the experiences of field workers within the most populated state on future public policy that could be improved by the research presented. Through the study, bureaucracies can see how the implementation of mandates of labor policies have been affective or ineffective. These legislative bodies can also use this research to change the way in which implementation and reporting on public policy back to these legislative committees could be changed.

Field workers- This study provides information to field workers about the issues that many across the country can relate to. The research attempts to explain why these issues continue to persist within the agriculture industry. This research also provides advocacy about labor rights to individuals who are field workers and about improving their lives through political intervention.

California Residents- This study provides to many California residents the harsh realities of experiences of those within the CV, and what labor goes into providing food on their table. This research also highlights why the CV is important to everyone living in this state, and hopefully to change the narrative about the CV. The goal is to bring awareness and to start advocating for the improvement of living condition to those who work and reside within the CV.

Future Researchers- This study allows for future research to be done on the relationship between Latinx and Hispanic field workers of the CV and California economy. This also provides groundwork for future public health issues presented by personal interviews and influences future economic research on the CV.

The importance of this research is to educate and advocate about the future downfall of California's economy. The goal of this thesis is to evaluate the agriculture industry as a catalyst of the decrease of quality of life for the Latin and Hispanic fieldworker population within the CV. This thesis is divided into six chapters: chapter two will evaluate and establish peer reviewed articles to establish the methods to conduct the research as well as evaluating key

debates within this issue, chapter three evaluates the methodical approach of conducting this research, chapter four establishes the results from surveys conducted, chapter five establishes a connection and analysis of the data by providing connection of peer reviewed literature to the explanation of the conditions Latinx and Hispanic field workers within the CV as a direct result of the influences from the agriculture sector, and chapter six provides a final conclusion of the overall findings of this thesis.

LITERATURE REVIEW

California's Latinx and Hispanic population within the nineteen counties of the Central Valley is estimated to be 3.1 million (AMERICA COUNTS STAFF, 2021). Subsequently, through mainstream media and social economic status, this ethnic group in the United States is closely associated to working blue collar jobs, specifically working heavy manual labor jobs such as field work or construction. Blue-collar jobs in the United States, is often associated as a job that involves manual labor and gets compensated with a flat or hourly rate. These types of jobs are characterized by the working class of America. The foundation of blue-collar jobs in the United States, are the direct result of people not wanting to do the jobs that require manual labor. Therefore, these jobs are often associated with lower wages, and tough environments for labor. Thus, many immigrants from other countries, documented or undocumented, can find work in these types of jobs.

In California alone, 92% of farmworkers are Latinx and Hispanic with the top counties to have the largest number of farm workers to be Monterey, Fresno, and Kern counties (Rogers & Buttice, Ph.D, 2013). Figure 4. below shows the breakdown of each county across California and shows that majority of field workers in California reside in the San Joaquin Valley. While Figure 4., places the perspective of field worker density into perspective for residents of California, the use of Figure 5., shows the breakdown of the Latinx and Hispanic population density of each of the nineteen county in the CV. Figure 6., goes into further detail to explain the Latinx and Hispanic population per capita (100,000 per person) in each of the counties in the Central Valley. Through each of the figures we can see that the population of Hispanic and Latinx field workers in the CV increases as we travel south towards the boarder of California and Mexico. Through the graphs and economic journals, the majority of the agricultural output for California comes

from the southern counties of the Central Valley (Rogers & Buttice, Ph.D, 2013), because of the agricultural development within these areas. Therefore, the price of living, food, and transportation can be supported in communities, like barrios, in respect to the median household income of each county (see Figure 7.). This is associated to the low cost of labor within these counties, averaging \$30,000 in annual income for field workers in the state of California (KITROEF & MOHAN, 2017) (See Figure 8.). Because of the constant work from the agriculture industry in these communities, California remains the largest overall producer of agricultural goods by value in the United States. Through the work of fieldworkers, in specific Latinx and Hispanic, California has one of the largest agricultural regions in the world.

Figure 4. Data are estimates based on 2009-2011 ACS Public Use Microdata. The Census Bureau combines smaller counties into Public Use Microdata Areas (PUMAs). Each range/color represents one-fifth of all counties.

Figure 5. Hispanic or Latinx population percent by country for the nineteen counties in the Central Valley based on the 2020 Census. This figure shows that there is a predominantly Latinx and Hispanic population within the San Joaquin Valley region.

Figure 6. This graph breaks down the density of Hispanic and Latinx per capita (per 100,000 persons) in each country of the Central Valley based on the 2020 Census. This density map highlights the largest density of Latinx and Hispanic per capita to be in Fresno County. This is a direct result of Fresno County being the largest county to produce the most agricultural output each year.

Figure 7. This graph shows the median household income per county against the California median household income (\$75,235) based on the 2020 Census. The map highlights almost all the counties within the Central Valley are below the median household income of the state.

Figure 8. This map shows the average field worker wage in 2015 and it conveys that the highest paid fieldworkers are located on the west coastlines of California. This Graph establishes the evidence that field workers in the Central Valley are being paid less for more labor-intensive jobs, in regions that produce more agricultural output annually.

While California produced an estimate of \$61.7 million of the gross value of agriculture production (GDP) in 2019; the CV alone produced \$49.4 million of the \$61.7 million of agricultural output (California Department of Food and Agriculture, 2021). Despite the CV producing more than 80% of the gross value of agriculture production in 2019, field workers of the CV make almost all the production possible for California. The community of Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers of the CV face several disadvantages compared to the rest of California’s

population. Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers are at a higher risk for living in poverty, less likely to have health insurance, and lack the resources necessary to change their situation.

Correspondingly, the quality of health for Latinx and Hispanic field workers of the CV is decreasing and as a result the quality of life is deteriorating (Newel, 2017). This literature review will examine key concepts and ideas that will better contribute to the development of the socioeconomic status of Latinx and Hispanic field workers of the CV that will lead to the economic collapse of California due to the decrease of the quality of life for Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers. Additionally, it will illustrate how racial discrimination is deeply rooted in the agriculture sector and create more dimension to the harsh realities that many Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers must endure to survive within the CV.

Key Concepts, Theories and Studies

An essential component to this research is the understanding of how the development of the Californian agriculture sector has contributed to the economic development and the influence over public policy and regulation. The advancement of the agriculture industry in California allows for an understanding as to why the quality of life for Latinx and Hispanic's are decreasing. The research of this thesis will be focused on different public health theories/concepts to understand why the quality of life for Hispanic and Latinx field workers quality of life is decreasing. This thesis will also be expanding on the theories of life satisfaction and GDP to establish a culturally specific theory that will relate GDP to the quality of life known as Cultural Health Analysis Theory. Through the understanding of these public health theories and concepts, the understand of quality of life for Latinx and Hispanic field workers will be achieved. Therefore, using the information gathered from the PEN-3 Model via survey will be converted into quality-of-life index, the Cultural Health Analysis Theory will be used to

understand how the GDP has continued to increase at the expense of quality of life. Using these theories will show a relationship between the agricultural industry and how it has affected the quality of life for this community, resulting in the future economic collapse of California because of the agriculture sector unregulated practices.

Agricultural Development in California

As the agriculture industry continues to make an influence on the Californian economy; the unregulated and economic influence becomes more apparent throughout the development of the agricultural industry throughout the nation. With a 235-year-old history of the agricultural sector's development, California's agriculture system quickly grew as a stakeholder over future agricultural development (Johnston & McCalla). In the Giannini Foundation Special Report 04-1, found that there have been eighteen long standing drivers that have had major influence over the development of the state's agricultural sector (see Table 1.). As seen through these drivers, California has seen a flourishing boost to crop production and a reduction of livestock production because of environmental changes contributed to global warming and access to natural resources available within this region. This report continues to further establish the future developments and limitations of agricultural industry within the 21st century. The reduction of the development for this sector is directly related to the problematic drivers (water development, capital, labor, marketing and institutional innovation, infrastructure, research, education and extension, regulation, and resource competition) of the agriculture industry in California. The Giannini Foundation Special Report 04-1 directly and indirectly established a relationship between these limiting factors which are influenced by public policy. Changes within the agricultural industry also included a reconfiguration of state-wide production; therefore, reflecting positive feedback of increasing demands for California's agricultural to be products for domestic and export

markets. The withdrawal of land from agricultural production is in respect to the population growth in Southern California and Central Coast regions. Respectively with the withdraw of land in California and the growth in higher-valued perennial and vegetable production, displacing field crop production in the Central Valley. Therefore, shifts within the Central Valleys water delivery systems such as the production of the aquafer system of the CV has been induced by surface-water deliveries, especially in the San Joaquin Valley

Table 1. Historical Drivers of California Agriculture		
Long-Standing Drivers	Historical Drivers, 1769-2000	Problematic Drivers, 2000-2050
BIO-PHYSICAL	Climate, Soils, Water Development, Widening Suite of Products	Water Development
TECHNOLOGY AND INPUTS	Biological, Mechanical, Adaptive Pest Management, Transportation, Processing and Storage Technology	
ACCESS TO INPUTS	Capital, Labor	Capital, Labor
HUMAN CAPITAL	Production Management, Adaptive and Risk Management, Marketing and Institutional Innovation	Marketing and Institutional Innovation
DEMAND FACTORS	Population Growth, Economic Growth/Rising Incomes	
PUBLIC INVESTMENTS	Infrastructure; Research, Education and Extension	Infrastructure; Research, Education and Extension
Recent Entrants	Regulation, Resource Competition	Regulation, Resource Competition

Table 1. Explains the Historical Drivers to California's development in the agriculture industry. This table examines the drivers have stayed constant over the years, as seen by " long-standing drivers," and looks at the potential blockade of development in this industry. The "Historical Drivers" examine from the start of development of California's agriculture industry and observe this industry into the 21st century to show what were the obstacles the agriculture industry has overcome or may have to deal with in future of development.

California's agriculture industry is different than the rest of the nation's demand of agriculture output. The rest of the United States has been solely a "supply driven" industry that has its historical roots in small homesteaders with the intent to feed themselves and their community (Dimitri, Effland, & Conklin, 2005). Whereas California's agriculture industry began with large farms, ranches, and rancheros that would produce more than can be consumed locally. As a direct result, California's began to meet other countries needs for livestock and crops that

needed to be harvested. With the foundation of California's agriculture industry split between livestock and crops, the share of the value of agricultural product sales coming from plant sources rose at the expense of animal products because of increases in intensive crops, crops that require intensive manual labor (Johnston & McCalla).

Within a 50-year development, California expanded their commodity of crops from 1970 with 200 crop commodities, to 2000 with 350 crop commodities, to 2021 with 400 crop commodities (California Department of Food and Agriculture, 2021). As California's crops became more diverse, the switch between basic crops to specialty crops meant that California's agriculture sector became less influenced and dependent on the rest of the nation's agriculture output. Ergo in 2017, California accounted for nearly 12% of the United States total agriculture sales (Keough, 2021), while the share of federal direct payments was only 1.5% (Economic Reserach Service, Government payments by program, 2022). Therefore, California's agriculture industry is constantly adapting and changing to adjust to the environmental factors that have persisted over time and have influenced the development within this sector. These driving factors of California's agriculture industry have caused new developments in farming equipment, water delivery systems, genetically modified crop commodities, and newer technology to be sold at cheaper rate. Thus, began California's influence over the industry.

PEN-3 Model

A major development within public health advancement has been with the introduction of culture as an aspect to an individual health. The recent push for culture as an essential part of public health development is a result of the need for cultural competency to promote public health. Cultural competency is an encompassing idea with ethical and racial differences factoring

into different cultures health outcomes (Evidence-based Practice Center Systematic Review P, 2014). Cultural competency takes on the perspective of understanding the ethnic disparities a group may face resulting in a decrease of quality health. This concept looks at the ethnic group and examines those who are at risk for stigmatization and discrimination. With the nation developing and the increase of diversity, culture has become a focal point in public health to understanding the decrease in health-related quality of life across many groups of ethnicities. To understand how culture plays an essential role the PEN-3 model is used to understand how culture factors into quality of life.

Culture is defined as a shared group of values, norms, religion, codes, and ethics that then shape and group's beliefs, ideals, and mottos (Airhihenbuwa , 1999). The PEN-3 model places culture at the center of this model, and it is explained by, "The PEN-3 cultural model consists of three primary domains: (1) Cultural Identity, (2) Relationships and Expectations, and (3) Cultural Empowerment. Each domain includes three factors that form the acronym PEN; Person, *Extended* Family, Neighborhood (Cultural Identity domain); Perceptions, Enablers, and Nurturers (relationship and expectations domain); *Positive*, *Existential* and *Negative* (Cultural Empowerment domain)," (Iwelunmor, Newsome, & Airhihenbuwa, 2014) (see Figure. 9) . To date, the PEN-3 model has been used to address problems associated with HIV, cancer, hypertension, diabetes, malaria, nutrition, smoking, and other issues requiring an understanding not only of behavior but also related to cultural contexts. At the end of the study done in 2014, by Iwelunmor, Newsome, & Airhihenbuwa, they found that the PEN-3 cultural model offers as a useful tool to express the impact of culture on target populations and to address the health issues and problems. This is done through the acknowledgement of aspects of culture that has negatively affected or influence the health of those within the culture.

Figure 9. Shows the relationship between each of the primary domains of the PEN-3 Model. This model conveys the impacts of behavior on health is the cultural empowerment domain, key influences on health behaviors is the relationship and expectations domain and focus on intervention is the cultural identity domain. The PEN-3 model places culture at the center of this model to address the health issues and problems in a targeted population.

In 2006, a study using the PEN-3 model, was able to examine the sociocultural factors associated with health and health care among Latinas. What they found was, “Participants identified both positive and negative perceptions, enablers, and nurturers associated with health maintenance and health care seeking. Participants acknowledged the importance of physical, mental, and spiritual health and what they should do to be healthy. Despite such knowledge, they tended to engage in unhealthy behaviors due to a variety of non-structural barriers such as lack of time, ‘tradition,’ and procrastination. They tended to use alternative/complementary medicine first, and then seek medical help if these practices are not effective. Many women believe that they do not have control over their own health attributing this lack of control to the ‘system,’” (Garcés,

Scarinci, & Harrison, 2006). Through this approach, we can then use the PEN-3 model as a tool to create a survey in the basis of culture to develop variables that then can be calculate for quality-of-life index. By using the PEN-3 model, further analysis of health within the Latinx and Hispanic fieldworker population of the CV can be understood from the quality-of-life index in a culturally competent way. The PEN-3 model allows for culture to be placed in the center to focus on this research and through this model we can explain how the cultural motivates the Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers within the CV to continue to put their health at risk as a result to cultural influences.

Quality of Life

The quality of life is an umbrella term describing multiple factors that contribute to determining if quality of life is increasing or decreasing (see Figure. 10). The quality of life is an overarching term that is encompassed by health-related quality of life, health perception, functional status, and psychosocial status to help understand how the quality of life is being affected (Moser, n.d.). The health-related quality of life is defined as an individual's perception of impact of disease and illness presented on their physical, emotional, and economic aspects in relation to their lives. Health-related quality of life is multidimensional, and therefore there are multiple factors that affect this aspect (Moser, n.d.) (see Table. 2). Health perception is a subjective rating that the individual gives by the affects that have contributed to their health status (Lee & Oh, 2013). Furthermore, as this being a subjective term there is the possibility that faced with constant chronic illness, the individual may still deem themselves as healthy despite the illness and exposures they have faced. Functional status is defined as the level of activities that an individual does to realize the needs of daily living (Wang, 2004). Therefore, this aspect, of quality of life, encompasses the activities (physical, psychological, spiritual, intellectual, and

roles) that contribute to daily activities that contribute to promoting health within the daily lives of these individuals. The psychosocial status is a term that is defined by the mental, emotional, social, and spiritual effects of disease prevalence (Marcia, 1993). Psychosocial status is the intersection of cultural, social, and environmental influences that contribute to the behavior of individuals. Through this research, the quality of life will be determined through a culturally developed survey of these key factors to determine and confirm that the quality of life for Latinx and Hispanic field workers of the Central Valley.

Figure 10. Shows the umbrella term of the overall quality of life. The figure shows how each of the concepts are related in determining the quality of life. This figure shows how there are three concepts that are core to the health-related quality of life is influenced.

Dimensions	Examples
Physical and occupational function, functional capacity	- independence and mobility- intellectual capacity- activities of daily living- job, leisure, and hobby activities- social activities- sexual functioning
Psychological state	- anxiety- depression- anger and hostility
Social interactions	- family/significant others- extended family- friends- vocational- community
Somatic sensations, health perceptions	- symptoms- perceptions about health status

Table 2. Shows the dimensions of health-related quality of life. This table also shows examples of what each of these dimensions are. This table highlights the importance of asking multiple questions to help get an overall understanding of an individual’s health-related quality of life.

Through the development of this thesis, the understanding of how these core concepts related to the of quality of life, have affected the outcomes of the Latinx and Hispanic field worker population within the CV. A study in 2021 examined the “well-being,” or quality of life, among Latina field workers in rural Idaho. This study examined a multitude of factors that contribute to the overall well-being of this targeted population. What the study shows, were the emerging of six major themes that emerged as primary challenges within this population. The major contribution of the lack of well-being in the population was working long hours, concerns of pesticide exposure, and lack of enforcement of regulatory practices (Curl, Meierotto, & Som Castellano, 2021). While this study does take place in Idaho, the study can be expanded to provide a foundation of understanding as to why the quality of life is being affected by the agricultural industry.

Through the development of this thesis, the use of the PEN-3 Model will be used to understand the health-related quality of life, health perception, functional status, and psychosocial status to develop the quality-of-life index for Latinx and Hispanic field workers of the CV. The Quality of Life Index is defined as, “...an overall look at the health and literacy of a country, state, or city and can be used to identify areas of the index that should be improved,”

(Williams & Wood-Dauphinee, 1989). Furthermore, the quality of life index will show the rankings of each country, state, or city and may further break down certain aspects of the quality of life of each for an expanded view. By using the quality of life index to explain the quality of life we are able to statistically show the decrease of quality of life for Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers within the CV.

Looking at the agricultural industry's development in recent years, and throughout the history of California, the correlation between the quality of life and the Latinx and Hispanic field worker population of the CV will be established. Through this establishment between the decrease of quality of life for Latinx and Hispanic field worker population of the CV and the development of the agricultural industry in California, the structural and systematic inequality that this population faces will then be related to uncontrolled and unregulated practices of the agricultural industry. Therefore, as the quality of life for the Latinx and Hispanic fieldworker population of the CV decreases as the result of California's agriculture industry contribution to the economy. The economic collapse of California is bound to happen as a direct result of the decrease of quality of life for the Latinx and Hispanic field worker population of the CV.

Key Debates and Controversies

There are many points of conflict within this thesis. There are four main controversy's that have come about from the research presented. There is the issue of documented and undocumented immigrants working in the fields and the idea of immigration within the United States. Another issue that was presented was caused by a governmental policy, Labor Standards Act, and the lack of regulation extending into the agricultural sector. Another point of interest is the expansion of the life satisfaction related to growth of the GDP to create the Cultural Health Analysis Theory to explain the quality of life to GDP. The largest issue that this thesis will deal

with is the development of California's infrastructure and its tolls on the Latinx and Hispanic fieldworker population within the CV. These controversy's come from societal issues that become present in social determinates of health along with issues of policy within the state of California and the United States government. This section of this thesis will discuss these issues and prove the necessity to discuss these issues that are happening to the Latinx and Hispanic field worker population of the Central Valley.

Documented vs. Undocumented Field Workers

To understand this issue that this thesis faces, the understanding of what a documented and undocumented immigrant is defined in the constitution if the United States. The United States Citizen and Immigration Services refers to the idea of legal immigration as someone who has been granted the authorization to stay and work within the United States on a permeant status. The United States Citizen and Immigration Services further defines what a documented immigrant is within the eye of the law. Defining this term as, "Any person not a natural born citizen of the United States who is residing the in the U.S. under legally recognized and lawfully recorded permanent residence as an immigrant. Also known as 'Permanent Resident Alien,' 'Resident Alien Permit Holder,' and 'Green Card Holder,' (U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, n.d.).

Until 2013, the associated press used to refer to "undocumented" immigrants/migrants as "illegal," rather they have now decided to call the action illegal immigration and the group undocumented immigrants (Colford, 2013). Until 2021, the use of "illegal alien," was used throughout the United States Immigration Law. Under the Biden Administration the language was replaced to "undocumented citizen," (Rose, 2021). This term of undocumented immigrant is defined broadly to all immigrants who reside within the United States without a legal status.

Undocumented immigrant includes all individuals who: entered without presenting themselves for inspection, someone who has entered legally but has remained in the country past their visas expiration date, people who once/have/eligible for Deferred Action for Childhood Arrivals (DACA), an individual who is going through the process to become a legal citizen of the United States, and someone who is a vulnerable immigrant that could be targeted by immigration enforcement (DEFINING UNDOCUMENTED). This idea of documented and undocumented is a social construct idea created by political entities and racist policies in attempts to create a barrier between those who were born in the United States and those who were not. Through the development of this social idea of immigration status, the polarized stances of right winged politicians have allowed this idea to become widely accepted across the United States. Thus, the quality of life for Hispanic and Latinx documented, and undocumented immigrants' lives are being but at risk to keep the California and United States economy from crashing.

In a study by Gleason in 2010, Gleason discuss the issues that both documented and undocumented immigrants face within their respective industry, in the case of this article restaurants. Gleason's research provides evidence how legal documentation status shapes the legal consciousness of immigrants within the United States. Through Gleason's research he found that the immigrants, regardless of their documentation status and knowing of the existing protections and resources, they still choose to not to come forward about the unregulated practices within different industries. In the findings of this study, Gleason also argued that undocumented status fundamentally shifts the legal consciousness of these workers, and any effort to improve their working conditions must also consider immigration policies that currently make it nearly impossible for most low-skill workers to legally enter the United States (Gleason, 2010). This article provides evidence of the harsh attitudes of American culture has created for

undocumented and documented immigrants. The treatment of immigrants regardless of their documented status shows the quality of life decreasing through accepting of lower wages in attempts to hide their documentation status from employers. This research provides the attitudes and opinions of most of Americans about the Latinx and Hispanic workers within this country.

The fact is, not all immigration is supposed to be perceived as a threat. The social dominance theory is a related construct. Prejudice may emerge from threat to the privileged status of the in-group members, also known as white Americans. Authoritarianism is thought to have developed from the opposition to change, whereas social dominance is motivated by desire to self-enhance. Both are, however, related to negative attitudes toward immigrants. In study conducted in 2009, the researchers found that attitudes toward the undocumented immigrants is minimal (Larsen, Krutov, Van Le, Ommundsen, & Veer, 2007). Those who are in power of politics use the debates of ideologically based and broadly defined as perspectives of the immigrant as a lawbreaker. The solutions that researchers came up with from the right seek the control of immigrants, while recognizing their value as cheap labor.

Compromises on this issue look for increased legal immigration to meet the needs of the economy, and some proponents note defensively that the complaints made about illegal immigration can also be made of legal immigrants. Solutions from the left emphasize the need of significant economic aid to source countries, and the elementary human rights as well as political refugees. Those within this issue use the debate matters, as shown in several studies, as a product for producing alternative meanings, policies, and constrains on immigration, creating a barrier to possible solutions. A radical solution would require economic as well as political restructuring in both source and host countries (Larsen, Krutov, Van Le, Ommundsen, & Veer, 2007). Through this article, we see that immigration status is used as a political ploy affecting the quality of lives

for immigrants in America. The researchers acknowledge the issues of immigration rights based on policy affecting the environments and social consciousness of immigrants in the United States. Furthermore, leading to a reconstruction of the entire structure of immigration policies. The reconstruction of the entire structure of immigration policies is aimed at improving the quality of life for the immigrants and strengthen the economic quality of America.

Labor Standards Act

The Fair Labor Standards Act was established under the Franklin D. Roosevelt Administration to provide workers with minimum wage, overtime pay, and child labor protections (Mayer, Collins, & Bradley, 2013). While we have assumed that the Fair Labor Standards Act would extend to the agricultural industry, this act does not help protect the wages and protections of fieldworkers in the agricultural industry. Understanding that the Fair Labor Standards Act was set into place for, “The specific efforts of southern congressmen to protect southern society, agriculture, and racism from federal interference is fact. The specific New Deal discrimination against minority farmworkers is fact. The identity of the beneficiaries of the farm worker exclusion from the Fair Labor Standards Act southern agricultural employers and the victim’s minority agricultural employees-is fact. Last, the continued disparate impact of the agricultural exclusion is fact,” (Linder, 1987). The understanding of why the Fair Labor Standards Act was established provides evidence that racial discrimination is deeply rooted in the United States public policy. The issues of race and discrimination have transcended history and is still relevant within our society today. The Fair Labor Standards Act provides evidence that the United States never cared about the rights of fieldworkers because of racist attitudes of Southern Democrats. The reality of this is American public policy seen through Fair Labor Standards Act, Occupational Safety and Health Act, Worker Protection Standard, and

Certification of Pesticide Applicators Standard as a way for the agricultural sector to be exempt from regulation and faces many structural issues, (Runyan).

Current legislation on the labor practices of the agriculture sector violates democratic ideals and the prevalence of racial and gendered justice for farm workers have not been met. In an article produced in 1998, the researcher investigated agricultural exceptionalism within public policy and legislation implemented within the United States. What they found, was with the increase of consumer consumption and demand of fruits and vegetables. The concern of food and safety should compel the reconsideration of working conditions for fieldworkers. The research of this study found that through the rapid demand of these items, the return of asking other countries for labor support is being lobbied by agricultural industries experts (Luna, 1998). This would affect the Chicano/Chicana fieldworkers and as a result the continued mistreatment of fieldworkers would persist. The value system sustaining agricultural exceptionalism is no longer acceptable. Agricultural history illustrates that New Deal programs, "...had only one aim: to raise farm prices and intentionally excluded a class of workers largely comprised of Chicana/Chicano laborers. The broad array of public law that gave birth to the wealth of agriculture is contrary to the place afforded farming in American history. Including all workers in the rural economy requires identifying and eliminating legal structures adversely affecting workers. In sum, it will effectively transform farm worker conditions that have persisted long beyond the imaginable (Luna, 1998).

Cultural Health Analysis Theory

Current research on this topic has not developed fast enough to explain the relationship between quality of life and GDP with respect to culture of a population. Therefore, the development of this thesis is expanding on the relationship between GDP and life satisfaction to

pioneer a public health theory that is known as the Cultural Health Analysis Theory. This theory is set out to bridge the two fields of Public Health and Economics in respect to culture. The Cultural Health Analysis Theory is based in using empirical data collected from a survey to explain the quality of life for a certain culture in respect to GDP growth of the state that the targeted population is located in. Furthermore, the Cultural Health Analysis Theory is a culturally competent theory that uses aspects of the PEN-3 Model to understand the quality of life to a targeted population in respect to culture, as different cultures will have different qualities of life. Through understanding the quality of life, then trends of the GDP will be explored to convey a relationship between the two variables to produce a cultural understanding of health issues of the targeted population in respect to the relationship between the variables. Thus, allowing a prediction to quality of life if the trend explored between the GDP and the populations quality of life continues to persist.

Providing a foundation of this theory, many studies have showed a relationship between life satisfaction and GDP. A study in 2013, conveyed the relationship between developing countries and developed countries GDP alongside of life satisfaction. From their study, the researchers found that the relationship between life satisfaction and GDP increases in countries with GDP below 15,000 USD and flattens in countries with higher GDPs (Proto & Rustichini, 2013). Furthermore, Proto and Rustichini found that in countries with a per capita GDP around 15,000 USD had a lower probability of 12% in reporting highest levels of satisfaction, and that life satisfaction peaks around 91,000 USD per capita GDP and then significantly declines among the richer countries (2013). Therefore, this study explains that life satisfaction increases with GDP in developing countries, but the relationship between developed countries is approximately flat.

While this study does provide statistically significant results between life satisfaction and GDP, this relationship is limited in explaining health related issues in the context of culture. This explanation of the relationship ignores the different cultures in each of the countries, and this limits the understanding in context of life satisfaction in relation to GDP. This relationship between life satisfaction is strictly monotonical. The Cultural Health Analysis Theory attempts to address this issue that the relationship between the two is neither increasing nor decreasing. Instead, this relationship between quality of life and GDP is dependent on the culture of the population the study is taking place in. Ignoring the context of culture in research limits the understanding of the data collection, as culture plays an essential role in interpreting peoples understanding of life satisfaction, or attributes that relate to the quality of life.

The Cultural Health Analysis Theory is expanding on the idea of life satisfaction and expanding quality of life to an entire population rather than the individual level. Life satisfaction is defined as how happy a population is (Proto & Rustichini, 2013). While life satisfaction has been used to relate a country's quality of life through happiness there are many limitations using this approach and the Cultural Health Analysis attends to address these issues while placing culture at the forefront of the relationship. Life satisfaction is an errored approach as individuals have different meanings of happiness, and happiness is dependent on the person psyche. Therefore, life satisfaction is not a standard variable that researchers can use to determine quality of life. The Cultural Health Analysis Theory attempts to address this issue by using a culturally competent understanding of quality of life at the individual level to become a standard variable for all participants in this study. Furthermore, the Cultural Health Analysis Theory expands quality of life from an individual level to a population by ensuring that the quality of life

determined is standardized through the use of culture. Providing a basis for the future development of this theory.

Development of California's Infrastructure on Farmland

California's farmland is being bought at a high rate because these areas are favored by good weather, flat terrain, and access to water (Sanders, 1998). As California continues to grow as a social hub for the rest of the nation, the push for farmland conservation needs to happen to ensure that California's economy does not collapse. Farmland conservation is defined as the act of conserving farmland from being bought and used for urban development and to protect the environment around the area (FACT SHEET WHY SAVE FARMLAND?). As California continues to develop its infrastructure to connect Northern California to Southern California, the lives of Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers in the CV suffer.

As we have seen from decades of debates in California politics, the issue of high-speed rail raises concern for the lives of Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers. Until 2008, California couldn't sell any of its bonds to begin developing the high-speed rail to connect all of California. When California residents, in 2008, voted, California was able to sell \$9.9 billion in bonds to afford this project. Through a \$3.3 billion grant from the American Recovery and Reinvestment Act (Nixon, Holian, Niles, & Pogodzinski, 2018), California was able to begin constructing the high-speed rail. Then in 2013, an executive report was released, and this report estimated the cost of the total project to be \$63.2 billion in 2011 (inflation-adjusted dollars) (Vranich & Cox, 2013). Since then, literature of the High-Speed Rail has been limited. The development of this project was sold to the Californian people for one price and since then, through political intervention, this this has exceeded the funding. While this isn't an issue that this thesis directly deals with, the High-Speed rail has affected the CV in more ways than any other part of California. More in

specific, the Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers of the CV have been tremendously affected by this infrastructure development, caused by the contractual grants that the government is giving to farmers of the Central Valley. While farmers are selling their land to make room for the High-Speed Rail (BRIEFING: November 14, 2012 AGENDA ITEM #5, 2012), the essential land for agriculture is being used to connect the state.

While there are many great benefits of the high-speed rail project; such as, the rail system will lower greenhouse emission and will bring jobs to the station cities (Karpman, 2021), this is not the reality of the situation. In a Report from 2013, it claims that, “The advent of high-speed rail in the [Central] Valley could also mean greater loss of the region’s invaluable agricultural resources to development. California agriculture is a \$43 billion per year industry and represents the world’s fifth-largest supplier of food and other agriculture commodities to a national and international market,” (Elkind, Hecht, & Horowitz, 2013). The report further looks at how the continued growth of this project from Phase 1 to Phase 2 will be detrimental to the CV.

Throughout this thesis, the stress of improving the quality of life for Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers of the CV has been of importance. With the continued development of the High-Speed Rail, there will not be any critical farmland left for Hispanic or Latinx fieldworkers of the CV to work on, and eventually the California economy will crash.

A large part of California’s economy comes from the agriculture industry, specifically the specialty fruits and vegetable and livestock industries, both are which the most labor intensive (BENEFITS OF FARMLAND CONSERVATION IN CALIFORNIA , 2015). Many fruit and vegetable crops that happen to be in California are maintained and harvested by hand and therefore are dependent on fieldworkers. The United States Department of Agriculture Census of Agriculture indicated that California farms spent \$5.9 billion on hired labor, \$3.4 billion on

contracted labor and \$1.3 billion on custom labor or custom hauling in 2012. Custom hauling is known as business for hire system and is a common practice when dealing with undocumented immigrants. We can see that from the United States Department of Agriculture Census of Agriculture, an essential component to the California economy is the hired work and comes from the agricultural industry of California (BENEFITS OF FARMLAND CONSERVATION IN CALIFORNIA , 2015). The hired work of the agriculture industry is 92% Latinx and Hispanic according to the United States Census Bureau (United States Census Bureau, 2012). To continue to allow California's transportation infrastructure to develop at the expense of farmland; is to allow California's economy to crash. The Californian economy is highly dependent on the agricultural output; therefore, to allow farmland to be used at the extent of connecting Northern California to Southern California is trivial. The amount of money that Californians are spending on this project should be going into improving the lives of the Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers of the CV to continue to their support and contribution to the economic growth of California.

Gaps in Existing Knowledge

The consistent missing piece throughout the literature of this topic is connecting the issues of Latinx and Hispanic fieldworker population of the CV and the economy of California. This thesis will attempt to fill in this knowledge by showing the adverse effects of living life below poverty and struggling to survive by working harsh jobs that many Latinx and Hispanic fieldworker population of the CV must take on. This thesis attempts to show how the Latinx and Hispanic field workers of this region of California feed the United States while their lives are taken for advantage. This issue will be explored by using surveys of Latinx and Hispanic fieldworker population of the CV and convey the relationship between GDP and the quality of life. By calculating the Quality of Life index for three different regions of the CV, the Health

Analysis Theory will be used to provide a culturally competent relationship between quality of life and GDP growth. Through this, the understanding of the trials and tribulation of the Latinx and Hispanic fieldworker population of the CV will be achieved. Throughout the development of this thesis, the importance of the lives of Hispanic and Latinx fieldworkers of the CV have on the California economy. This thesis will show California's future economic collapse directly relates to the sociopolitical factors affecting the quality of life for Latinx/Hispanic fieldworkers within the Central Valley. As the GDP of California continues to increase, the quality of life for Latinx/Hispanic fieldworkers continues to decrease at the hands of the agriculture sectors unregulated practices.

METHODS

The approach that this study takes on a mixed methods approach utilizing surveys to calculate the Quality of Life Index to then explore trends in GDP growth in California and to evaluate the relationship between quality of life and GDP growth. The first step of this thesis is to gain a background of the demographics, region, sociopolitical, health systems, and health disparities of the CV is through exploring databases, literature, and historical context of cities in the CV to understand the culture of this region. Understanding the culture of the CV is essential to providing a foundation of the lives of the Latinx and Hispanic fieldworker population of the CV. Establishing this background will lay the foundation for the rest of this thesis. The following step will be creating consent forms in both English and Spanish (see Appendix A) and formulating a survey for each of the targeted groups of this thesis (documented, undocumented Hispanic and Latinx field/farm workers). Knowing that majority of immigrants only speak Spanish, it is essential to provide the consent forms in English and Spanish.

Development of the Questionnaire

The questionnaire for this thesis, uses a culturally competent based questions that will be able to calculate for the quality of life index. The important aspect of the questionnaire is ensuring that these questions are culturally competent to the Latinx/Hispanic fieldworker community in the CV. Because this questionnaire will be culturally competent, the questionnaire will be offered in both English and Spanish. There ten areas this questionnaire will be testing for: health status; employment and occupancy rate status; quality of lifetime work status; income status; consumption status; environment and accommodation status; education status; safety, law and order and corruption status; moral-ethical, spiritual, cultural values and leisure time status; and gender equality status (Puskorius, 2015). These ten areas that are being tested for will be

used to calculate the quality of life index that will then be able to look at the individual level of Latinx/Hispanic fieldworkers in the CV.

These areas that are being tested in the questionnaire must be culturally competent to ensure that the questions being asked are understood in a cultural aspect. To do this, the PEN-3 model will be used to guide and shape the questions for this thesis. The PEN-3 model places culture at the center of this model, and it is explained by, “The PEN-3 cultural model consists of three primary domains: (1) Cultural Identity, (2) Relationships and Expectations, and (3) Cultural Empowerment. Each domain includes three factors that form the acronym PEN; Person, *Extended* Family, Neighborhood (Cultural Identity domain); Perceptions, Enablers, and Nurturers (relationship and expectations domain); *Positive*, *Existential* and *Negative* (Cultural Empowerment domain),” (Iwelunmor, Newsome, & Airhihenbuwa, 2014). This model will guide the questions to ensuring that each of the testing variables will be supported in a culturally competent understanding.

The questionnaire will be conducted using the Qualtrics program, that will be offered in English and Spanish. This questionnaire will have 86 questions that the participants of this research will be asked to complete and will be stored on a computer that will have a multi-factor authentication (see Appendix B). This is used to protect the vulnerable population within this thesis. The participants in this research will all be given unique participant identifiers to protect this community and the consent forms will be protected by the principal investigator. This will be done by labeling the participants on their consent forms and locked in a safe that is away from the principal investigator home. The collection of data will be done in person face to face in the field of the Central Valley. This will be done by the principal investigator and proper PPE will be used, such as facemasks; gloves; hand sanitizer; outdoor locations; and social distancing, to

prevent the spread of COVID-19 to this community. Once the data from the survey has been collected, all the data will be transferred into SPSS to further calculate the Quality-of-Life Index.

Selection of Participants

The process of selecting informants will be done in a way to mitigate the bias of the principal investigator and limiting the confounding variables that arises while conducting the survey. To ensure that bias is mitigated, the select our informants will be collected from a cluster of fields around the Central Valley. Using a cluster sample method to mitigate the biases, is essential to breaking down the CV into three sections (see Appendix C) to get a variety of respondents from the informants. Using a cluster sampling method, each of the subgroups of the three regions of the CV have similar characteristics. Which is why Placer County will be excluded from this research. Placer County is part of the Central Valley, but majority of this county is found in the Sierra Nevada Mountain. Placer county also has a lower poverty (5%) rate and a higher median household income (\$93,677) compared to the rest of the counties in California (AMERICA COUNTS STAFF, 2021). As a result, Placer County is different from the rest of the counties found in the CV and will be excluded from the development of the cluster sampling for the collection of responses.

Breaking this region into three major sections of the CV allows for bias to be limited but not eliminated. There will always be a possibility of bias, therefore the design of this research will consider response bias when conducting the analysis of the surveys. The result of response bias is contributed to the fact that the informants are choosing to respond to the questions the principal investigator is asking. There is also a possibility that the informants could lie or give misleading information that could change the outcome of the research. Because of the possibility for response bias, the research must take into consideration the possibility of lying occurring in

any of the informants, retaliation on the documented and undocumented Hispanic and Latinx field/farm workers by farmers for choosing to speak with the principal investigator, or the possibility that this study will face backlash. In the selection of participants, minors will not be included because that would require a consent form for the parent, and occasionally children working out in the field do not have their parents there. We will also will not be using white fieldworkers because we are looking at the Latinx/Hispanic field worker population. Using a cluster sampling method, each of the subgroups of the three regions of the CV have similar characteristics. Which is why Placer County will be excluded from this research. Placer County is part of the Central Valley, but majority of this county is found in the Sierra Nevada Mountain. Placer county also has a lower poverty (5%) rate and a higher median household income (\$93,677) compared to the rest of the counties in California (AMERICA COUNTS STAFF, 2021). As a result, Placer County is different from the rest of the counties found in the Central Valley and will be excluded from the development of the cluster sampling for survey responses.

Breaking the CV into three parts, and excluding Placer County, allows for each of the parts to have an equal number of counties. By ensuring that there is an equal number of counties in each part of the CV, allows for an equal chance for each county to be represented in this project. As a result, each county in each part of the CV will be given a number 01-06 (see Appendix D), and a simple random number generator will randomly select a number three times. These 3 random numbers will be representing the county the principal investigator will travel to, to collect responses. The sample size of this project will be a minimum of 100 respondents as this would provide proof of statistical significance within this project. The breakdown of this number will have at least 35 respondents in each county to get a sample size of 105. The selection of each participant will be by choosing field in that county that have fieldworkers

working. By doing this, it makes the data accessible and ensures that this data is only dealing with Latinx/Hispanic fieldworkers of the CV.

Calculating for the Quality of Life Index

Using SPSS, the quality of life index for each of participant is made possible through programing the calculations of quality of life index. For each of question the questionnaire has, each response is associated with a score. These scores will then be used to calculate that indicators/variables weight to the quality of life. For example, having a higher income status would positively affect income status versus someone saying that they defiantly believe that crime is a problem in their neighborhood would negatively affect safety, law and order and corruption status. The formula that is being used in this thesis to calculate the quality of life index is:

$$I = \sum_{i=1}^{10} a_i b_i,$$

where b_1 ; a_1 –value of summarized health status indicator of population (b_1) and weight coefficient of this indicator (a_1) correspondingly; b_2 ; a_2 –value of summarized employment and occupancy rate status of population (b_2) and weight coefficient of this indicator (a_2) correspondingly; b_3 ; a_3 –value of summarized quality of lifetime work status indicator of population (b_3) and weight coefficient of this indicator (a_3) correspondingly; b_4 ; a_4 –value of summarized income status indicator of population (b_4) and weight coefficient of this indicator (a_4) correspondingly; b_5 ; a_5 –value of summarized consumption status indicator of population (b_5) and weight coefficient of this indicator (a_5) correspondingly; b_6 ; a_6 –value of summarized environment and accommodation status indicator of population (b_6) and weight coefficient of this indicator (a_6) correspondingly; b_7 ; a_7 –value of summarized education status indicator of

population (b_7) and weight coefficient of this indicator (a_7) correspondingly; b_8 ; a_8 —value of summarized safety, law and order and corruption status indicator of population (b_8) and weight coefficient of this indicator (a_8) correspondingly; b_9 ; a_9 —value of summarized moral-ethical, spiritual, cultural values and leisure time status indicator of population (b_9) and weight coefficient of this indicator (a_9) correspondingly; b_{10} ; a_{10} —value of summarized gender equality indicator of population (b_{10}) and weight coefficient of this indicator (a_{10}) correspondingly (Puskorius, 2015).

To calculate the coefficient of the indicator, the PEN-3 model, and Maslow's hierarchical list of motives will be used to figure out this coefficient. The PEN-3 Model will be used to ensure that this research is considering the Latinx/Hispanic community in the CV. This will also be used to guide Maslow's hierarchical list of motives. Maslow's hierarchical list of motives explains that there are five levels of human needs. These five needs are: psychological, security, communication, respect, and recognition in the community (Maslow, 1955). Using Maslow's theory, these needs must be arranged in a strict hierarchy which would place important human needs at a high level, only when the lower level needs have been satisfied. Along with this theory and model, calculating the coefficient of the indicator relies on statistical data that is available in that specific community. By doing this, the coefficient of the indicator will be found and able to calculate the quality of life index for that individual.

Since this thesis depends on the use of a survey the formula that will be used to calculate the indicator of population in the targeted variable will use the calculation method of:

$$b_i = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^5 kn_k$$

Where, b_i –value of whatever indicator calculated using survey data of population; N –total number of respondents, who expressed their opinion replying this question; k –number of attached scores by respondents; n_k – number of respondents, who attached score k (Puskorius, 2015). By calculating for indicator of population and the coefficient of the indicator we can calculate for the quality of life index for the individual.

Comparison of Quality of Life Index and GDP

Once all the responses have been collected, and the quality of life for each individual has been calculated, the data analysis will begin. How this thesis will compare the quality of life index to the GDP of California is by pulling on primary and secondary data to see the growth trends of the GDP in California. By seeing the trends of GDP growth in California contextualized, this project will compare this growth to the quality of life for Latinx/Hispanic fieldworkers within the CV. This process will be done through the Cultural Health Analysis Theory that this project has created. The Cultural Health Analysis will be used to convey the trends of GDP growth compared to quality of life index based in a culturally competent understanding.

Practical Considerations

This research does present many potential obstacles, limitations, and ethical and practical issues. Some of the potential obstacles that this research presents and must overcome are finding study participants who are willing to share their experiences about working in the fields as a documented or undocumented worker and enhancing outside-of-the-classroom research fits into the standardized practice of research. The limitations that this research presents is time along with timing of study, and access to literature. This study also faces ethical issues such as: dealing

with economically disadvantaged and vulnerable groups, conflicts of interest, and potential for harm.

Overcoming these obstacles that the research presents, must be overcome by preserving. When faced with the answer of “No, I don’t want to participate in this study,” the perseverance to find another informant must happen. This must happen to provide the essential data to this project and spread awareness about the mistreatment of field workers within the Central Valley. To overcome this obstacle of rejection, an environment of security for those who are undocumented must be cultivated to ensure that we are able to protect the informant from all retaliation for advocating about their experiences within this industry. Another obstacle that this project must overcome is by connecting the data to the foundational research. This will be done through acknowledging that the data is going to be less than perfect and therefore it is alright that the data and research do not match all the time. Another way that this research can overcome this issue is by possibly expanding the relationships between the groups or even collect more responses to the survey.

The limitations of the research design are small but not significant to discrediting the information that is presented. There are nearly seven million people who live in the CV and 348,900 people are employed through agriculture industry (California Department of Food and Agriculture, 2021). Therefore, only surveying a minimum of 100 people does not correlate to the size of the population. While this may be significant to those who are only relying on quantitative data, this project is dealing with qualitative data and using primary and secondary sources as the quantitative data to provide more evidence to the position of the research. Time is another limitation that this research is faced with. Time along with timing of study is something that this project can overcome by creating a timeline on deadlines of when a certain aspect of the

research project should be done. This is to ensure that all components of the project are met and are on track with submitted the project time it is need. Another limitation that this research project faces is the issue of access to the comparison of field workers to the California economy. Specifically, the CV does not have a lot of literature on the topic, so having to find information on these issues is difficult. To overcome this obstacle is through conducting foundational research at local libraries in the Central Valley, looking at hospital data, and using local news sources and information to provide context on the culture of the Central Valley. As well as using that information from these sources to correlate the decrease of quality of life in the Latinx and Hispanic field worker population of the Central Valley, to the future economic collapse of California.

This research must take into consideration that the targeted population is an economically disadvantaged and vulnerable group. Through keeping the names of the informants from being released at all, destroying the survey responses after the study is submitted and providing resources to those who have been interviewed will ensure that this group is protected from retaliation. The design of this research plans to ensure the informants that they do not have to participate if it places a burden on their family or themselves. Within this study there are conflicts of interest and that must deal with personal biases. Growing up in the Central Valley, the constant mistreatment of farm labors has been persistent over the years. As a result, there are person investment within this project which could influence some personal bias. To overcome this obstacle, the research will be reviewed by the advisors, and an outside source who has no influence over this project will also review to ensure that there are no biases present in the completion of this project. Ensuring this component of the project is met, having a nonbiased set of eyes reviewing the project, would limit the possibility of having a personal bias present in the

work. This project also presents an ethical issue of potential for harm to the informants. This could be caused by the employer becoming mad at the informant for speaking to the primary investigator for this research project. This project will deal with this issue by ensuring that the informant is off the clock, the employer is nowhere near the informant when the interview is happening, and the informant is provided resources to legally protect them from possible retaliation. This project would also ensure that the names of the informants stay anonymous throughout this project and there could be no possible trace to the informant.

Implications and Contributions to Knowledge

The life of a farmworker isn't important to people. The reality is that the machinery of growers is taken better care of than the lives of farmworkers. Most farmers wouldn't take a machine out into the field without putting oil in it, so how can they take the life of a person and not even give them the basics? The culture within the CV is failing. Residents in this region are dying at younger ages than most of the country because of the lack of equitable healthcare for all, and the unregulated practices of the agriculture industry. Fieldworkers within this region are facing pollution, pesticide, contaminated water, heat illnesses, non-regulated working conditions, and many other societal issues; it's no longer a class or racial issue. It's to the point where regardless of who you are, how you want to identify, and where you live these issues that those who live in the CV face, affect everyone.

Practical Implications

This project provides practical implications for two major contributions: (1) informing policy maker and (2) make a case for concrete change in the agriculture industry. This project will provide substantial evidence to the understanding of the quality of life for field workers in the CV. This project lays out information for future healthcare policy dealing with immigration

status and the issues of receiving health care. Healthcare policy can be shaped by this project by looking at what areas of life for field workers are affected the most by current policies prohibiting the access to healthcare based on immigration status. This project also provides information for future workers regulation policies that can be implanted within this industry. By providing contextual data from peer reviewed articles along with providing an analysis of survey from the informants on the issues that field workers face. The future development of worker rights policies can be shaped from the data and information this project provides. This information can be used to create positive change in the labor rights sector of the agriculture industry, as well as expanding protective services to workers in this industry.

This project also brings about a concern for change within our society and challenges the status quo. This project challenges the current idea of what a field workers life is expected to be by presenting the issues that go unsaid within this industry. This project sheds a light on public health, economic, and political issues in attempt to gain and educate support to cause future change to our society. By bringing light to this issue, it could lead the way to helping the CV's continued economic growth and protect the fieldworkers who have placed their lives at risk to feed America. This project presents a case of concern to create drastic change within the State of California. Furthermore, this project transcends the State of California and calls for drastic change in the United States to protect the lives of field workers across the nation.

Theoretical Implications

The work of this project will strengthen models like the PEN-3 model and the Cultural Health Analysis Theory for purposes of understand the social determinates of health along with environmental influences on health. The use of these models, this project expands the idea of public health models to help explain the effects of an industry has on the quality of life for

individuals. Through these adverse effects of environmental factors, political regulations, and the understanding of societal issues we can then better interpret the data that we receive from the informants. Allowing for a contextualization of the background through the analysis of survey data of the Latinx and Hispanic fieldworker. Because of these models and theories, this project will lay a foundation for future research.

RESULTS

The data that was collected was during the year of 2023 in the fields of the CV. This gave the opportunity to survey over 100 participants in order to prove statistical significance in the population. The results of the survey can be found in Appendix D. Using this information collected from each respondent, a numeric point value system was created to determine the Quality of life Index for this study. The data suggests that there is a heavy emphasis on health status indicated by Table 3. Understanding these values that were tested helps develop an understanding of the cultural understanding/awareness and the values that this population has on itself. It also helped to determine the coefficients that were needed to calculate the quality of life for each participant in the study.

Average for Gender Equality Status	Average for Gender Equality Status2	Average Safety, Law and Order and Corruption Status	Average environment and accommodation status	Average consumption Status	Average Employment and Occupation Status	Average Health Status	Average Quality of Lifetime Work Status	Average Income Status
6.758152958	2.839480519	7.34972583	6.25015873	10.16904762	7.034391534	12.54201601	6.127966742	5.87978

Table 3. is the average for each variable that this study was investigating. This understanding helps provide a conceptualization of what was the biggest issues that fieldworkers in the Central Valley face.

Understanding that each population in this survey faces, a descriptive statistic was ran on SPSS to show the mean of each population that was surveyed. The data shows that those who were born in the United States have a better quality of life versus their counterparts. Undocumented women in this study show that they have a lower quality of life in total. Whereas natural born men have the highest quality of life in this study. Documented women have a higher

quality of life versus documented men, but this could be because of the sample size of males in this study.

Doc_stat	Gender	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Undocumented	female	68.1983	5.31275	26
	male	69.2301	5.57369	24
	Total	68.6936	5.40868	50
documented	female	71.3839	5.23040	14
	male	70.6939	3.18944	4
	Total	71.2305	4.77519	18
natural	female	73.8552	4.14430	16
	male	74.5184	3.77710	21
	Total	74.2316	3.89784	37
Total	female	70.6109	5.47227	56
	male	71.6160	5.29797	49
	Total	71.0800	5.38936	105

Table 4. highlights the descriptive statistics of each population in this study. The data suggests that males typically have a better quality of life compared to females. This shows that there needs to be more health incentives for women in this community of the Central Valley.

Table 5. shows the QOL index for Latinx/Hispanic Fieldworkers within the CV for each participant. This data is vital to be used for the Cultural Health Analysis Theory. Using the methods that this study described, we were able to create and establish the quality of life index for each of the participants to graph against the quality of life index that the United States claims that as a country we are at. This data is ensured to be culturally competent as this data ensures that cultural awareness is placed at the forefront of the data collection. From this data we did have four outliers, but they were not excluding from the calculation of the results as the data is significant at $p < 0.001$. If that data was not significant, we would have excluded them from that data.

QOL Index for Latinx/Hispanic Fieldworkers	
	59.06305916
	61.17667148

62.06541607
62.78114478
64.2986051
65.06866282
65.13727754
65.62813853
65.86608947
66.23121693
66.29201539
67.54689755
67.75079365
67.89201539
68.71459836
68.83333333
68.88552189
68.9990861
69.66560847
70.18475228
70.66661857
71.2961039
72.7048581
75.27609428
75.49482739
85.63573834
53.48518519
61.31707552
63.21428571
65.150481
65.75300625
66.43090428
67.77388167
68.24834055
69.20904281
69.2984608
69.40632516
69.47676768
69.8037037
69.87441077
70.45743146

70.51308321
71.04776335
71.11293891
71.2015873
72.88547379
72.97053872
74.09494949
74.12631073
84.67147667
64.4012987
64.67017797
67.12424242
67.84117364
68.55921116
69.25502646
71.12032227
71.91014911
72.06065416
72.27710438
73.58823954
75.33877234
76.9999038
84.22770563
66.04247234
71.33203463
72.24146224
73.15959596
67.04239094
67.89023569
69.82837903
70.21568062
70.34651275
72.40697451
72.92106782
73.12433862
73.53386243
74.08999519
77.48706109
77.71890332

77.88903319
78.07219817
78.33915344
80.77758538
69.64723425
69.71101491
70.2987494
70.37445887
70.39196729
71.95478595
72.79187109
73.2044733
73.35512266
73.51005291
73.76628187
74.9012025
75.32212602
76.14131794
76.16536797
76.20507456
76.39023569
77.36363636
79.03756614
79.53516114
84.81871092

Table 5. This data is all the participants in this study’s quality of life that was calculated from the methods section of this thesis. In this data set we do have 4 outliers, but they were not excluded from the data set because we have to emphasis cultural competency, and some may have acclimated to the culture of the United States better than others.

Table 6. shows an ANOVA analysis conducted on between groups. The analysis was conducted on Latinx/Hispanic QOL, Gender, and documented status. What this data suggest is that documentation status does affect the quality of life for Latinx/Hispanic fieldworkers. This is shown to be significant because $F(9,13.268) < 0.001$. Therefore, documentation does determine

how Latinx/Hispanic Fieldworkers of the CV’s QOL is being affected. Whereas gender does not affect quality of life because $F(0.083) .774 > 0.001$. In a culturally competent understanding the results suggest that being acclimated into American culture affects someone’s quality of life.

Dependent Variable: Latinx_QOL

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	671.432 ^a	5	134.286	5.659	<.001
Intercept	357806.826	1	357806.826	15078.252	<.001
Doc_stat	629.697	2	314.848	13.268	<.001
Gender	1.974	1	1.974	.083	.774
Doc_stat * Gender	7.387	2	3.693	.156	.856
Error	2349.269	99	23.730		
Total	533518.875	105			
Corrected Total	3020.702	104			

a. R Squared = .222 (Adjusted R Squared = .183)

Table 6. ANOVA Analysis ran on SPSS between the quality of life for Latinx/Hispanic fieldworkers in the Central Valley, Documentation Status, and Gender. This Table highlights that documentation status is an important factor when determining the quality of life for Latinx/Hispanic fieldworkers in the Central Valley as $F(12.268) < 0.001$.

Figure 11. below highlighting the disparity of the rest of the United States versus the quality of life for Latinx/Hispanic fieldworkers in the CV. The x axis is the number of participants that participated in this study, and the y-axis is the quality of life index. Where this thesis had 105 participants. The quality of life for the United States is 170.72 (Cullum Clark, 2022), whereas the average quality of life for both men and women fieldworkers, regardless of documentation status, is 71.0800. On the graph the first spike shows undocumented men, then from the dip to the next spike is undocumented men, following the next spike is documented women, the little hump is documented men, then the next spike is natural born women, and the final length of the graph is documented men. There could have been more documented men in this study, and if repeated that would place a factor into graphing. This graph highlights the

disparities between each group by being graphed in groups of documentation status and gender. Compared to the quality of life of the United States, there is a clear disparity between fieldworkers in the CV compared to the quality of life for the United States.

Figure 11. Compares the quality of life for Latinx/Hispanic fieldworkers in the Central Valley compared to that of the overall USA quality of life. The graph highlights the disparity between blue collar groups in America and the rest of the population. The quality of life for Latinx/Hispanic fieldworkers in the Central Valley is broken down by documentation status and gender.

Using the data from Table 5, a Z-Score was created for everyone that participated. The reason why a z-score was created was to standardize the data that was collected to be compared to the growth of the GDP. Table 7, highlights this information by showing each participants z-score. The mean of the population was 71.0800 to keep the data consistent with one another. This information is essential to comparing the data to the growth of the GDP in California. By

doing this, an analysis can be performed to predict the future quality of life for Latinx/Hispanic fieldworkers in the CV.

Z-score for Individual QOL Index Score
-2.22975
-1.83757
-1.67266
-1.53986
-1.25829
-1.1154
-1.10267
-1.01159
-0.96744
-0.89969
-0.88841
-0.65557
-0.61773
-0.59153
-0.4389
-0.41687
-0.40718
-0.38611
-0.26244
-0.16611
-0.0767
0.0401
0.3015
0.77859
0.81918
2.70083
-3.26473
-1.81151
-1.45949
-1.10022
-0.98842
-0.86264
-0.61345

-0.52541
-0.34715
-0.33056
-0.31055
-0.29748
-0.23681
-0.22369
-0.11551
-0.10519
-0.00598
0.00612
0.02256
0.33501
0.35079
0.55943
0.56525
2.52191
-1.23923
-1.18934
-0.73399
-0.60096
-0.46773
-0.33862
0.00749
0.15404
0.18196
0.22213
0.46541
0.79022
1.09845
2.43957
-0.93471
0.04677
0.21551
0.38587
-0.74918
-0.59186
-0.23224
-0.16037

-0.1361
0.24622
0.34162
0.37933
0.45532
0.55851
1.18884
1.23186
1.26343
1.29741
1.34695
1.7994
-0.26585
-0.25401
-0.14496
-0.13091
-0.12766
0.16232
0.31764
0.3942
0.42215
0.4509
0.49845
0.70903
0.78713
0.93914
0.9436
0.95097
0.98532
1.16594
1.47654
1.56887
2.54923

Table 7. This data is all the participants in this study's standardized quality of life that was calculated from Table 5. In this data set we do have 4 outliers, but they were not excluded from the data set because we have to emphasis cultural competency, and some may have acclimated to the culture of the United States better than others.

Figure 12. shows the relationship between the GDP growth of California (0.04%) (BEA, 2023) versus the z-score of the Latinx/Hispanic fieldworkers' quality of life in the CV. The first group of points on the left are undocumented women, next set of plots are undocumented men, then documented women, the small cluster next to documented women is documented men, then natural born women, and finally natural born men. Comparing the two groups, we see that there is a clear disparity between GDP growth in California and the QOL for Latinx/Hispanic fieldworkers within the CV. On Figure 12., there are still four outliers that are present within the data set.

Figure 12. GDP Growth of California's Economy (0.04%) vs. Z-Score for Latinx/Hispanic Fieldworker's QOL Index Score. As the GDP growth continues, the QOL Index continues to decrease. The graph highlights the disparity between blue collar groups in America and the rest of the population. The quality of life for Latinx/Hispanic fieldworkers in the Central Valley is broken down by documentation status and gender.

Figure 13. below, Shows the forecasting of the next year of the z score for the Latinx/Hispanic Fieldworker population within the CV. This data was achieved by using a forecasting sequence on SPSS to predict the next year of quality of life for all Latinx/Hispanic Fieldworker population within the CV regardless of gender and documentation status. The forecasting sequence is symbolized by the black line within the figure. In this scenario, we are also assuming that the growth of California's GDP will continue to grow at the rate of 0.04%. To ensure that this data was significant we ran a paired T-test of differences between the continued growth of California's GDP and the forecasting of the z score in the Latinx/Hispanic Fieldworker population within the CV.

Figure 13. Continued Growth of California's GDP (0.004%) vs. Forecast of QOL for Latinx/Hispanic Fieldworker population within the Central Valley. Figure 13. Highlights the continued disparities between fieldworkers within the Central Valley and the growth of the GDP. Which suggests that this could lead to a worse recession than Californians are already in.

The t-test that was used was a paired t-test of differences between the continued growth of California's GDP and the forecast of QOL for Latinx/Hispanic Fieldworker population within the Central Valley. Our null hypothesis is that there is no difference between the continued growth of California's GDP and the forecast of QOL for Latinx/Hispanic Fieldworker population

within the Central Valley. Our alternative hypothesis is that there is a clear difference between the continued growth of California's GDP and the forecast of QOL for Latinx/Hispanic Fieldworker population within the Central Valley.

H_0 : continued growth of California's GDP = forecast of QOL for Latinx/Hispanic FW

H_a : continued growth of California's GDP \neq forecast of QOL for Latinx/Hispanic FW

When running this test, we see conducted this test on SPSS. The statistics that SPSS gave are highlighted by Table 8., Table 9., Table 10., and Table 11. Table 9., highlights that there is a moderate correlation ($r = 0.750$) between the two groups. This table highlights that there is a relationship between the continued growth of California's GDP and the forecast of QOL for Latinx/Hispanic Fieldworker population within the Central Valley. Furthermore Table 10. Shows the statistical information of the paired t-test of differences between the continued growth of California's GDP and the forecast of QOL for Latinx/Hispanic Fieldworker population within the Central Valley. From the data we know that there is a clear difference between the continued growth of California's GDP and the forecast of QOL for Latinx/Hispanic Fieldworker population within the Central Valley because $t(565.234) < 0.001$, with a confidence interval of (4.38573, 4.41685). As a result, we must reject the null and accept the alternative hypothesis that there is a clear difference between the continued growth of California's GDP and the forecast of QOL for Latinx/Hispanic Fieldworker population within the Central Valley

Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Cont_GDP_Groqth_Prediction_2023	5.5211	64	.04111	.00514
	Forecast_Z_QOL	1.1198	64	.08687	.01086

Table 8. Shows the paired sample statistics of the paired t-test that was ran. This table highlights the descriptive statistics for each of the groups that we are running.

Paired Samples Correlations

		N	Correlation	Significance	
				One-Sided p	Two-Sided p
Pair 1	Cont_GDP_Groqth_Prediction_2023 & Forecast_Z_QOL	64	.750	<.001	<.001

Table 9. Shows the correlation between California's GDP growth and the forecast of z-scores in the Latinx/Hispanic fieldworker population within the Central Valley. Where $R=0.750$ which suggest that there is a moderate correlation between the two. We see that this information is significant to the running of this test because $p < 0.001$.

Paired Samples Test

		Paired Differences					Significance			
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	One-Sided p	Two-Sided p
					Lower	Upper				
Pair 1	Cont_GDP_Groqth_Prediction_2023 - Forecast_Z_QOL	4.40129	.06229	.00779	4.38573	4.41685	565.234	63	<.001	<.001

Table 10. Is the statistical information for the paired t-test of differences between the GDP growth of California and the forecast of z-scores in the Latinx/Hispanic fieldworker population within the Central Valley. We know that there is a clear difference between the growth of California's GDP and the forecast of z-scores in the Latinx/Hispanic fieldworker population within the Central Valley because $t (565.234) < 0.001$, with a confidence interval of (4.38573, 4.41685).

Paired Samples Effect Sizes

Pair 1	Cont_GDP_Groqth_Prediction_2023 - Forecast_Z_QOL		Standardizera	Point Estimate	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper
		Cohen's d	.06229	70.654	58.335	82.950
		Hedges' correction	.06267	70.233	57.987	82.455

a. The denominator used in estimating the effect sizes.
 Cohen's d uses the sample standard deviation of the mean difference.
 Hedges' correction uses the sample standard deviation of the mean difference, plus a correction factor.

Table 11. Shows the effect size of the paired t-test of differences between the GDP growth of California and the forecast of z-scores in the Latinx/Hispanic fieldworker population within the Central Valley. This t-test also used Cohen's and Hedges' correlation test to ensure that the data was significant in comparing the two groups.

DISCUSSION

Using the Cultural Health Analysis Theory, we can assume that these findings are culturally competent in the context of the Latinx/Hispanic fieldworker population. The data suggest that there is a clear health disparity between this group and the rest of America, meaning that there needs to be a solution at the local and state level of government to prove the lives of these people. The data shows that these disparities will continue to persist through the next year if things do not improve meaning that we must fight against the injustices facing this community. Furthermore, we see that the data shows that the most vulnerable community we see within this study are those who are undocumented. This group is the most vulnerable to facing instances of pesticide poisonings, housing crisis, and employment based abuse. This idea of documented and undocumented is a social construct idea created by political entities and racist policies in attempts to create a barrier between those who were born in the United States and those who were not. Through the development of this social idea of immigration status, the polarized stances of right winged politicians have allowed this idea to become widely accepted across the United States. Thus, the quality of life for Hispanic and Latinx documented, and undocumented immigrants' lives are being but at risk to keep the California and United States economy from crashing. Leading to the question of what are we doing to prevent these issues from persisting?

The harsh reality is that there is nothing that we are doing to fix these issues that are happening within this community. It shows how this ethnic group is closely associated to working blue collar jobs, specifically working heavy manual labor jobs such as field work or construction. It shows that farmworkers are at a higher risk for living in poverty, less likely to have health insurance, and lack the resources necessary to change their situation. If things do not change, we will see a collapse in California's GDP. The US Department of Agriculture indicated that

California farms spent \$5.9 billion on hired labor, \$3.4 billion on contracted labor and \$1.3 billion on custom labor. If we want to keep this 49.1 billion dollar industry, then we need these workers. These Latinx/Hispanic fieldworkers in the CV are facing pollution, pesticide, contaminated water, heat illnesses, non-regulated working conditions, and many other societal issues; it's no longer a class or racial issue. It's to the point where regardless of who you are, how you want to identify, and where you live these issues that Latinx/Hispanic fieldworkers in the CV face, affect everyone.

Looking closer at the data, we see that there were some increases within Figure 13., while this would seem that the QOL is increasing for this group, the reality is that those spikes are because of different society factors that improve the lives for a little bit then the data decreases. This could be because of social empowerment within the community, laws that have been implemented at the state level that is affecting those who are within the community and working conditions that have improved overtime because of strikes. The Cultural Health Analysis shows that these spikes are explained because of factors that contribute to the quality of life. Furthermore, the Cultural Health Analysis Theory explains more about California's farmland is being bought at a high rate because these areas are favored by good weather, flat terrain, and access to water (Sanders, 1998). As California continues to grow as a social hub for the rest of the nation, the push for farmland conservation needs to happen to ensure that California's economy does not collapse. Farmland conservation is defined as the act of conserving farmland from being bought and used for urban development and to protect the environment around the area (FACT SHEET WHY SAVE FARMLAND?). As California continues to develop its infrastructure to connect Northern California to Southern California, the lives of Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers in the CV suffer.

Thus, the Cultural Health Analysis takes into consideration that California produced an estimate of \$61.7 million of the gross value of agriculture production (GDP) in 2019; the CV alone produced \$49.4 million of the \$61.7 million of agricultural output (California Department of Food and Agriculture, 2021). Despite the CV producing more than 80% of the gross value of agriculture production in 2019, field workers of the CV make almost all the production possible for California. The community of Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers of the CV face several disadvantages compared to the rest of California's population. Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers are at a higher risk for living in poverty, less likely to have health insurance, and lack the resources necessary to change their situation. Correspondingly, the quality of health for Latinx and Hispanic field workers of the CV is decreasing and as a result the quality of life is deteriorating (Newel, 2017). This literature review will examine key concepts and ideas that will better contribute to the development of the socioeconomic status of Latinx and Hispanic field workers of the CV that will lead to the economic collapse of California due to the decrease of the quality of life for Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers. Additionally, it will illustrate how racial discrimination is deeply rooted in the agriculture sector and create more dimension to the harsh realities that many Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers must endure to survive within the CV.

Furthermore, current legislation on the labor practices of the agriculture sector violates democratic ideals and the prevalence of racial and gendered justice for farm workers have not been met. In an article produced in 1998, the researcher investigated agricultural exceptionalism within public policy and legislation implemented within the United States. What they found, was with the increase of consumer consumption and demand of fruits and vegetables. The concern of food and safety should compel the reconsideration of working conditions for fieldworkers. The research of this study found that through the rapid demand of these items, the return of asking

other countries for labor support is being lobbied by agricultural industries experts (Luna, 1998). This would affect the Chicano/Chicana fieldworkers and as a result the continued mistreatment of fieldworkers would persist. The value system sustaining agricultural exceptionalism is no longer acceptable. Agricultural history illustrates that New Deal programs, "...had only one aim: to raise farm prices and intentionally excluded a class of workers largely comprised of Chicana/Chicano laborers. The broad array of public law that gave birth to the wealth of agriculture is contrary to the place afforded farming in American history. Including all workers in the rural economy requires identifying and eliminating legal structures adversely affecting workers. In sum, it will effectively transform farm worker conditions that have persisted long beyond the imaginable (Luna, 1998).

The data shows that this region is an important part of-not only California's economy-but the entire United States. This region of California faces some of the highest rates of human trafficking rates, unregulated working conditions, homelessness, police brutality, domestic violence, drug use, high rates of high school to prison pipeline, insufficient healthcare systems, and a high teen pregnancy rate (Rosales, 2012). The CV is solely dependent on the agriculture industry's development. If we continue to allow the quality of life for Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers to decrease; then we are allowing an industry that spends \$5.9 billion on hired labor, \$3.4 billion on contracted labor and \$1.3 billion on custom labor (BENEFITS OF FARMLAND CONSERVATION IN CALIFORNIA , 2015), to destroy an economy that was built on the shoulders of Latinx and Hispanic fieldworker. If we want to keep this 55-billion-dollar industry from crashing down on itself, then the time to start improving the quality of life for Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers within the CV begins now.

As the agriculture industry continues to make an influence on the Californian economy; the unregulated and economic influence becomes more apparent throughout the development of the agricultural industry throughout the nation. With a 235-year-old history of the agricultural sector's development, California's agriculture system quickly grew as a stakeholder over future agricultural development (Johnston & McCalla). In the Giannini Foundation Special Report 04-1, found that there have been eighteen long standing drivers that have had major influence over the development of the state's agricultural sector (see Table 1.). As seen through these drivers, California has seen a flourishing boost to crop production and a reduction of livestock production because of environmental changes contributed to global warming and access to natural resources available within this region. This report continues to further establish the future developments and limitations of agricultural industry within the 21st century. The reduction of the development for this sector is directly related to the problematic drivers (water development, capital, labor, marketing and institutional innovation, infrastructure, research, education and extension, regulation, and resource competition) of the agriculture industry in California.

The Giannini Foundation Special Report 04-1 directly and indirectly established a relationship between these limiting factors which are influenced by public policy. Changes within the agricultural industry also included a reconfiguration of state-wide production; therefore, reflecting positive feedback of increasing demands for California's agricultural to be products for domestic and export markets. The withdrawal of land from agricultural production is in respect to the population growth in Southern California and Central Coast regions. Respectively with the withdraw of land in California and the growth in higher-valued perennial and vegetable production, displacing field crop production in the Central Valley. Therefore, shifts within the Central Valleys water delivery systems such as the production of the aquafer

system of the CV has been induced by surface-water deliveries, especially in the San Joaquin Valley

California's agriculture industry is different than the rest of the nation's demand of agriculture output. The rest of the United States has been solely a "supply driven" industry that has its historical roots in small homesteaders with the intent to feed themselves and their community (Dimitri, Effland, & Conklin, 2005). Whereas California's agriculture industry began with large farms, ranches, and rancheros that would produce more than can be consumed locally. As a direct result, California's began to meet other countries needs for livestock and crops that needed to be harvested. With the foundation of California's agriculture industry split between livestock and crops, the share of the value of agricultural product sales coming from plant sources rose at the expense of animal products because of increases in intensive crops, crops that require intensive manual labor (Johnston & McCalla).

Within a 50-year development, California expanded their commodity of crops from 1970 with 200 crop commodities, to 2000 with 350 crop commodities, to 2021 with 400 crop commodities (California Department of Food and Agriculture, 2021). As California's crops became more diverse, the switch between basic crops to specialty crops meant that California's agriculture sector became less influenced and dependent on the rest of the nation's agriculture output. Ergo in 2017, California accounted for nearly 12% of the United States total agriculture sales (Keough, 2021), while the share of federal direct payments was only 1.5% (Economic Reserach Service, Government payments by program, 2022). Therefore, California's agriculture industry is constantly adapting and changing to adjust to the environmental factors that have persisted over time and have influenced the development within this sector. These driving factors of California's agriculture industry have caused new developments in farming equipment, water

delivery systems, genetically modified crop commodities, and newer technology to be sold at cheaper rate. Thus, began California's influence over the industry.

Limitations

There are a few limitations that this study has. If this study was to be repeated, we would want to have a cohort of 200 participants and record their quality of life for over the course of 5 year. This way we can see how each individual's quality of life is being affected overtime. This is a major aspect we want to go over because this part of the process would be vital to future research within the development of this reserach.

CONCLUSION

The data allows for a culturally competent understanding of the relationship between QOL for Latinx/Hispanic fieldworkers in the CV and GDP growth in California. Because of the economic development of this state, this population's QOL is decreasing, leading to the state's economic collapse if health inequalities are not addressed. The data shows a clear difference between the average QOL Index for the USA (170.4) and Latinx/Hispanic fieldworker QOL Index. As a result, we must conclude that there are true health disparities in the Latinx/Hispanic fieldworker population in the CV making the QOL for this population to be significantly different than that of the USA. Through using the Cultural Health Analysis Theory, we see that the forecasting of Latinx/Hispanic fieldworker QOL Index is significant ($t = 565.234$, $p < 0.001$) when tested against the prediction of California's GDP growth in 2023. Therefore, using the Cultural Health Analysis Theory, we can assume that when the QOL Index is increasing, for a short amount of time, in Latinx/Hispanic fieldworkers' population of the CV, the understanding that health policies, cultural empowerment, law and safety in these communities could be improving.

When a specific group, like fieldworkers, have been overlooked and have become more excluded overtime, the possibilities of created political change through democratic institutions will continue to persist and become apparent to those within the community that is being overlooked. Focusing on fieldworkers' experiences within the fields of the CV can help develop more theories of ways to improve the quality of life for Latinx and Hispanic fieldworkers in the CV to help prevent an economic elapse, as well as potentially informing future public policy and legislation. Addressing this problem will have practical benefits to the economy and to the quality of living for Latinx and Hispanic field workers in the CV, while also contributing to the

wide spread of racial, societal, and structural issues that many face in this region of California. The life of a farmworker isn't important to people. The reality is that the machinery of growers is taken better care of than the lives of farmworkers. Most farmers wouldn't take a machine out into the field without putting oil in it, so how can they take the life of a person and not even give them the basics? The culture within the CV is failing. Residents in this region are dying at younger ages than most of the country because of the lack of equitable healthcare for all, and the unregulated practices of the agriculture industry. Fieldworkers within this region are facing pollution, pesticide, contaminated water, heat illnesses, non-regulated working conditions, and many other societal issues; it's no longer a class or racial issue. It's to the point where regardless of who you are, how you want to identify, and where you live these issues that those who live in the CV face, affect everyone.

APPENDIX

A. Consent forms in English and Spanish

I am asking you to participate in a research study titled “California’s Future Economic Collapse Due to a Decrease of Quality Life of Latinx/Hispanic Field Workers Within the Central Valley.” I will describe this study to you and answer any of your questions. This study is being led by Sonny Bianchi I, Honors Student at California State University, Fullerton. The **Faculty Advisor for this study** are Alexandro Gadilla, Department of Chicana and Chicano Studies.

What the study is about

The purpose of this research is to examine the decrease of quality of life within the Latinx and Hispanic fieldworker population in the Central Valley because of the economic contribution of the agriculture industry within California. This study sets out to explain the quality of life through surveys that are culturally competent and are based in the PEN-3 Mode. Through this the quality of life will be calculated and the trends will be explored through the Cultural Health Analysis theory. This study will also take into consideration different confounding variables such as the federal and state policy issues within this sector of industry. This research explains the methods and designs of conducting the study during the year of 2023.

Throughout this research, the combination of social health determinates and environmental factors of fieldworkers will be observed to explore how the quality of life is decreasing for Latinx and Hispanic field workers of this region of California. This research will also look at the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth caused by California’s agriculture sector influence, and how the growth of the Californian GDP has affected public policy to create negative changes in the lives of fieldworkers. Observing these issues and examining records of census, this research analyzes the trends of growth in California to show the correlation between the decrease of life caused by the agricultures unregulated practices on the environment of field workers, through the growth of the GDP.

This research stresses the importance of field workers within the Central Valley of California in relation to the California Economy and the lives of everyone in the country. This research stresses the economic effects on Latinx, and Hispanic field workers of the Central Valley caused by the agriculture sectors major influence on the economy and the state and federal public policy. This research sheds light on a community that supports a large part of the nation and discusses societal controversies. The aim of this research is to create change in the lives of Latinx and Hispanic field workers of the Central Valley.

What we will ask you to do

I will ask you to do, if you choose to participate within this research, to partake in a survey. In this survey I will ask you a few questions about your experiences working within the agriculture industry and how it has shaped your experiences in life. This survey will be personal but structured and should last no longer than 30 minutes.

Risks and discomforts

There are a few risks that come with participating in this research. The first being possible retaliation from employer as a direct result about communicating your experiences within the industry. There is another possible emotional risk within participating in this research, which could cause some anxiety or sadness talking about your experiences.

Benefits

This research provides practical implications for two major contributions: (1) informing policy maker and (2) make a case for concrete change in the agriculture industry. This research will provide substantial evidence to the understanding of the quality of life for field workers in the Central Valley. This research lays out information for future healthcare policy dealing with immigration status and the issues of receiving health care. Healthcare policy can be shaped by this research by looking at what areas of life for field workers are affected the most by current policies prohibiting the access to healthcare based on immigration status. This research also provides information for future workers regulation policies that can be implanted within this industry. By providing contextual data from peer reviewed articles along with providing a personal account from the informants on the issues that field workers face. The future development of worker rights policies can be shaped from the data and information this research provides. This information can be used to create positive change in the labor rights sector of the agriculture industry, as well as expanding protective services to workers in this industry.

This research also brings about a concern for change within our society and challenges the status quo. This research challenges the current idea of what a field workers life is expected to be by presenting the issues that go unsaid within this industry. This research sheds a light on public health, economic, and political issues in attempt to gain and educate support to cause future change to our society. By bringing light to this issue, it could lead the way to helping the Central Valley's continued economic growth and protect the field workers who have placed their lives at risk to feed America. This research presents a case of concern to create drastic change within the State of California. Furthermore, this research transcends the State of California and calls for drastic change in the United States to protect the lives of field workers across the nation.

Compensation for participation

There is no compensation in participating in this study.

Privacy/Confidentiality/Data Security

Throughout this research the goal is confidentiality between the data collector and the participants. Therefore, a participant label will be created as soon as there has been verbal agreeance for each participant to protect privacy and to prevent retaliation. The identify will be protected by using a computer in this research to aid in the storage the survey results using this device, the storage of the survey and photos will be filed on a secure password software to ensure the safety of the vulnerable population.

Your confidentiality will be kept to the degree permitted by the technology being used. We cannot guarantee against interception of data sent via the internet by third parties.

Taking part is voluntary

Taking part within this research is completely voluntary. You may refuse to participate before the survey begins, during the survey, or skip any questions that may make you feel uncomfortable. Withdrawing from the study will **NOT** result in any penalty from the university or other organization or service that may be involved with the research.

If you have questions

The main researcher conducting this study is Sonny Bianchi I, an undergraduate student at California State University, Fullerton. Please ask any questions you have now. If you have questions later, you may contact Sonny Bianchi I at sonnybianchi@csu.fullerton.edu or at (650) 300-9835. If you have any questions or concerns regarding your rights as a subject in this study, you may contact the Institutional Review Board (IRB) for Human Participants at 657-278-7719 or access their website at https://www.fullerton.edu/doresearch/compliance/irb_cayuse.php.

Statement of Consent

I have read the above information and have received answers to any questions I asked. I consent to take part in the study.

Your Signature _____ Date _____

Your Name (printed) _____

Signature of person obtaining consent _____ Date _____

Printed name of person obtaining consent _____

This consent form will be kept by the researcher for five years beyond the end of the study.

Le pido que participe en un estudio de investigación titulado "El colapso económico futuro de California debido a una disminución de la calidad de vida de los trabajadores de campo latinos dentro del Valle Central". Le describiré este estudio y responderé a cualquiera de sus preguntas. Este estudio está siendo dirigido por Sonny Bianchi I, estudiante de honores en la Universidad Estatal de California, Fullerton. Los asesores de la facultad para este estudio son Alexandro Gadilla, Departamento de Estudios Chicanos y Christopher Gibson, Departamento de Sociología.

De qué se trata el estudio

El propósito de esta investigación es examinar la disminución de la calidad de vida dentro de la población de trabajadores de campo latinos y hispanos en el Valle Central debido a la contribución económica de la industria agrícola dentro de California. Este estudio se propone explicar la calidad de vida con el uso de cuestionarios que son basados entre el PEN-3 Modo y culturalmente competente. Con esto la calidad de vida va ser calculado y las tendencias serán basadas con la teoría del análisis de salud culturalmente. Este estudio también tomara en consideración diferente variables como las pólizas federales y estatales entre la industria agrícola. Esta investigación explica los métodos y diseños de este estudio en el año de 2023.

A lo largo de esta investigación, se observará la combinación de determinados determinantes de salud social y factores ambientales de los trabajadores de campo para explorar cómo la calidad de vida está disminuyendo para los trabajadores de campo latinos y hispanos de esta región de California. Esta investigación también analizará el crecimiento del Producto Interno Bruto (PIB) causado por la influencia del sector agrícola de California, y cómo el crecimiento del PIB de California ha afectado las pólizas públicas para crear cambios negativos en las vidas de los trabajadores de campo. Observando estos problemas y examinando los registros del censo, esta investigación analiza las tendencias de crecimiento en California para mostrar la correlación entre la disminución de la vida causada por las prácticas no reguladas de la agricultura en el medio ambiente de los trabajadores de campo, a través del crecimiento del PIB.

Esta investigación enfatiza la importancia de los trabajadores de campo dentro del Valle Central de California en relación con la economía de California y la vida de todos en el país. Esta investigación enfatiza los efectos económicos en los trabajadores de campo latinos e hispanos del Valle Central causados por la gran influencia de los sectores agrícolas en la economía y la política pública estatal y federal. Esta investigación ilumina una comunidad que apoya a una gran parte de la nación y discute las controversias sociales. El objetivo de esta investigación es crear un cambio en las vidas de los trabajadores de campo latinos e hispanos del Valle Central.

Qué te pediremos que hagas

Le pediré que haga, si decide participar en esta investigación, participar en un cuestionario. En este cuestionario le haré algunas preguntas sobre sus experiencias trabajando dentro de la industria agrícola y cómo ha dado forma a sus experiencias en la vida. Este cuestionario será personal pero estructurada y no debe durar más de 30 minutos.

Riesgos e incomodidades

Hay algunos riesgos que vienen con la participación en esta investigación. La primera es una posible represalia del empleador como resultado directo de la comunicación de sus experiencias dentro de la industria. Existe otro posible riesgo emocional al participar en esta investigación, que podría causar algo de ansiedad o tristeza al hablar de sus experiencias.

Beneficios

Esta investigación proporciona implicaciones prácticas para dos contribuciones principales: (1) informar a los responsables de la formulación de pólizas y (2) defender un cambio concreto en la industria agrícola. Esta investigación proporcionará evidencia sustancial para la comprensión de la calidad de vida de los trabajadores de campo en el Valle Central. Esta investigación presenta información para futuras pólizas de atención médica relacionadas con el estado migratorio y los problemas de recibir atención médica. La póliza de atención médica puede ser moldeada por esta investigación al observar qué áreas de la vida de los trabajadores de campo se ven más afectadas por las pólizas actuales que prohíben el acceso a la atención médica en función del estado migratorio. Esta investigación también proporciona información para futuras pólizas de regulación de los trabajadores que se pueden implantar dentro de esta industria. Al proporcionar datos contextuales de artículos revisados por pares junto con proporcionar una cuenta personal de los informantes sobre los problemas que enfrentan los trabajadores de campo. El desarrollo futuro de las pólizas de derechos de los trabajadores puede configurarse a partir de los datos y la información que proporciona esta investigación. Esta información se puede utilizar para crear un cambio positivo en el sector de los derechos laborales de la industria agrícola, así como para ampliar los servicios de protección a los trabajadores de esta industria.

Esta investigación también genera una preocupación por el cambio dentro de nuestra sociedad y desafía el status quo. Esta investigación desafía la idea actual de lo que se espera que sea la vida de los trabajadores de campo al presentar los problemas que no se dicen dentro de esta industria. Esta investigación ilumina sobre temas de salud pública, económicos y políticos en un intento de obtener y educar apoyo para causar un cambio futuro en nuestra sociedad. Al traer luz a este problema, podría liderar el camino para ayudar al crecimiento económico continuo del Valle Central y proteger a los trabajadores de campo que han puesto sus vidas en riesgo para alimentar a los Estados Unidos. Esta investigación presenta un caso de preocupación para crear un cambio drástico dentro del Estado de California. Además, esta investigación trasciende el estado de California y pide un cambio drástico en los Estados Unidos para proteger las vidas de los trabajadores de campo en todo el país.

Compensación por participación

No hay compensación en participar en este estudio.

Privacidad/Confidencialidad/Seguridad de los datos

A lo largo de esta investigación el objetivo es la confidencialidad entre el recopilador de datos y el participante. Por lo tanto, se creará una etiqueta de participante tan pronto como haya habido un acuerdo verbal para cada participante para proteger la privacidad y evitar represalias. La identificación se protegerá mediante el uso de una computadora en esta investigación para ayudar en el almacenamiento de las grabaciones de audio en un dispositivo seguro para garantizar la privacidad y la protección de cada uno de los participantes. Mediante el uso de este dispositivo, el almacenamiento de el cuestionario y fotos se archivará en un software de contraseña segura para garantizar la seguridad de la población vulnerable.

Su confidencialidad se mantendrá en la medida permitida por la tecnología que se utilice. No podemos garantizar contra la interceptación de datos enviados a través de Internet por terceros.

La participación es voluntaria

Participar en esta investigación es completamente voluntario. Puede negarse a participar antes de que comience el cuestionario, durante el cuestionario u omitir cualquier pregunta que pueda hacer que se sienta incómodo.

Retirarse del estudio NO resultará en ninguna penalización de la universidad u otra organización o servicio que pueda estar involucrado con la investigación.

Si tiene preguntas

El investigador principal que realiza este estudio es Sonny Bianchi I, un estudiante de pregrado en la Universidad Estatal de California, Fullerton. Por favor, haga cualquier pregunta que tenga ahora. Si tiene preguntas más tarde, puede comunicarse con Sonny Bianchi I en sonnybianchi@csu.fullerton.edu o al (650) 300-9835. Si tiene alguna pregunta o inquietud con respecto a sus derechos como sujeto en este estudio, puede comunicarse con la Junta de Revisión Institucional (IRB) para Participantes Humanos al 657-278-7719 o acceder a su sitio web en https://www.fullerton.edu/doresearch/compliance/irb_cayuse.php.

Declaración de consentimiento

He leído la información anterior y he recibido respuestas a cualquier pregunta que haya hecho. Doy mi consentimiento para participar en el estudio.

Firma _____ Fecha _____

Su nombre (impreso) _____

Firma de la persona que obtiene el consentimiento _____ Fecha _____

Nombre impreso de la persona que obtiene el consentimiento _____

Este formulario de consentimiento será conservado por el investigador durante cinco años después del final del estudio.

B. Three Region Break Down of the CV

C. Three Region Break Down of the CV

D. Results of all survey questions

Consent to Survey - Do you consent to participate in this survey?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Do you consent to participate in this survey?	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Yes	100.00%	105
2	No	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	105

- What gender do you identify with?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	What gender do you identify with?	1.00	2.00	1.53	0.50	0.25	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Male	46.67%	49
2	Female	53.33%	56
3	Non-binary / third gender	0.00%	0
4	Prefer not to say	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	105

- What is your age?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	What is your age?	2.00	6.00	3.16	0.90	0.80	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Under 18	0.00%	0
2	18 - 24	23.81%	25
3	25 - 34	44.76%	47
4	35 - 44	23.81%	25
5	45 - 54	6.67%	7

6	55 - 64	0.95%	1
7	65 - 74	0.00%	0
8	75 - 84	0.00%	0
9	85 or older	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	105

- What is your documentation status?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	What is your documentation status?	1.00	4.00	2.15	0.94	0.89	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Natural Citizen	35.24%	37
2	Documented Immigrant	17.14%	18
3	Undocumented immigrant	44.76%	47
4	Prefer not to say	2.86%	3
	Total	100%	105

- What is your ethnicity?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	What is your ethnicity?	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	104

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Latino or Hispanic	100.00%	104
2	Caucasian	0.00%	0

3	African-American	0.00%	0
4	Asian	0.00%	0
5	Native American	0.00%	0
6	Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander	0.00%	0
7	Two or More	0.00%	0
8	Other/Unknown	0.00%	0
9	Prefer not to say	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	104

- Which county do you reside in?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Which county do you reside in?	1.00	18.00	8.85	5.75	33.12	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Shasta	30.48%	32
2	Tehama	2.86%	3
3	Glenn	0.00%	0
4	Butte	0.00%	0
5	Colusa	0.00%	0
6	Yuba	0.00%	0
7	Sutter	0.00%	0
8	Yolo	0.00%	0
9	Solano	0.00%	0
10	Sacramento	5.71%	6
11	San Joaquin	27.62%	29
12	Stainislus	0.00%	0
13	Merced	0.95%	1
14	Fresno	23.81%	25
15	Madera	1.90%	2
16	Kings	0.95%	1
17	Tulare	4.76%	5
18	Kern	0.95%	1
	Total	100%	105

- What is your martial status?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	What is your martial status?	1.00	6.00	3.63	1.85	3.41	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Married	31.43%	33
2	Widowed	0.95%	1
3	Divorced	3.81%	4
4	Separated	1.90%	2
5	Single	60.95%	64
6	Prefer not to say	0.95%	1
	Total	100%	105

- How many children do you have?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	How many children do you have?	1.00	4.00	1.80	0.95	0.90	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	None	53.33%	56
2	1	17.14%	18
3	2-4	25.71%	27
4	More than 4	3.81%	4
5	Prefer not to say	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	105

- How many people live in your home?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	How many people live in your home?	1.00	5.00	3.13	0.77	0.59	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	1	2.86%	3
2	2	11.43%	12
3	3-4	59.05%	62
4	5-6	22.86%	24
5	more than 6	3.81%	4
	Total	100%	105

- Which of the following describes your living status?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Which of the following describes your living status?	2.00	2.00	2.00	0.00	0.00	104

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Homeowner	0.00%	0
2	Renter	100.00%	104
3	Homeless	0.00%	0
4	Other	0.00%	0
5	Prefer not to say	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	104

- What is your highest level of education?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	What is your highest level of education?	1.00	6.00	2.28	1.26	1.59	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Elementary	38.10%	40
2	Middle School	23.81%	25

3	Some of High School	13.33%	14
4	High School or GRE	22.86%	24
5	Some of College	0.95%	1
6	Bachelor's	0.95%	1
7	Master's	0.00%	0
8	Ph.D. or Higher	0.00%	0
9	Trade School	0.00%	0
10	Prefer not to say	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	105

- What is your employment status?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	What is your employment status?	1.00	3.00	1.33	0.58	0.34	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Employed full time	72.38%	76
2	Employed part time	21.90%	23
3	Unemployed looking for work	5.71%	6
4	Unemployed not looking for work	0.00%	0
5	Retired	0.00%	0
6	Student	0.00%	0

7	Disabled	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	105

- What is your household income?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	What is your household income?	1.00	5.00	2.75	0.84	0.70	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Less than \$10,000	4.76%	5
2	\$10,000 - \$19,999	32.38%	34
3	\$20,000 - \$29,999	49.52%	52
4	\$30,000 - \$39,999	9.52%	10
5	\$40,000 - \$49,999	3.81%	4
6	\$50,000 - \$59,999	0.00%	0
7	\$60,000 - \$69,999	0.00%	0
8	\$70,000 - \$79,999	0.00%	0
9	\$80,000 - \$89,999	0.00%	0
10	\$90,000 - \$99,999	0.00%	0
11	\$100,000 - \$149,999	0.00%	0
12	More than \$150,000	0.00%	0
13	Prefer not to say	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	105

- Which languages are you capable of speaking fluently? (Check all that apply)

#	Answer	%	Count
1	English	31.37%	48
2	Spanish	68.63%	105
3	Portuguese	0.00%	0
4	French	0.00%	0
5	Mandarin	0.00%	0
6	Arabic	0.00%	0
7	Other	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	153

- Do you have health insurance?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Do you have health insurance?	2.00	3.00	2.81	0.39	0.15	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Yes, I have private	0.00%	0
2	Yes, I have public	19.05%	20
3	No	80.95%	85
	Total	100%	105

- How healthy do you consider yourself on a scale of 1 to 10? 1 being the worst and 10 being the best

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	How healthy do you consider yourself on a scale of 1 to 10? 1 being the worst and 10 being the best	4.00	10.00	8.85	1.14	1.29	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	1	0.00%	0
2	2	0.00%	0

3	3	0.00%	0
4	4	0.95%	1
5	5	1.90%	2
6	6	1.90%	2
7	7	3.81%	4
8	8	17.14%	18
9	9	46.67%	49
10	10	27.62%	29
	Total	100%	105

- How often do you get a health checkup?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	How often do you get a health checkup?	1.00	5.00	4.24	0.92	0.85	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Once every 3 months	4.76%	5
2	Once every 6 months	0.00%	0
3	Once a year	4.76%	5
4	Only when needed	47.62%	50
5	Never get it done	42.86%	45
6	Other	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	105

- What do you say about your overall health?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	What do you say about your overall health?	1.00	3.00	1.07	0.29	0.08	104

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Having Good Physical Health	94.23%	98
2	Moderately physically impaired	4.81%	5
3	Severely physically impaired	0.96%	1
4	Totally physically impaired	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	104

- Do you have any chronic diseases?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Do you have any chronic diseases?	1.00	2.00	1.08	0.27	0.07	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	No	92.38%	97
2	Yes	7.62%	8
3	prefer not to say	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	105

- Do you have any hereditary conditions/diseases?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Do you have any hereditary conditions/diseases?	1.00	2.00	1.91	0.28	0.08	104

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Yes	8.65%	9
2	No	91.35%	95
	Total	100%	104

- Are you habitual to drugs and alcohol?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Are you habitual to drugs and alcohol?	1.00	4.00	3.47	0.62	0.38	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Yes to both	0.95%	1
2	Only to drugs	3.81%	4
3	Only to alcohol	42.86%	45
4	I am not habituated to either	52.38%	55
	Total	100%	105

- Overall, how do you rate the local hospitals in your area?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Overall, how do you rate the local hospitals in your area?	1.00	5.00	3.27	0.92	0.84	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Excellent	3.81%	4
2	Above average	13.33%	14
3	Average	42.86%	45
4	Below average	32.38%	34
5	Very poor	7.62%	8
	Total	100%	105

- Please state your level of agreement to the statement: Health insurance is affordable to you.

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Please state your level of agreement to the statement: Health insurance is affordable to you.	1.00	5.00	2.25	0.93	0.87	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Completely Disagree	15.24%	16
2	Somewhat Disagree	60.95%	64
3	Neutral	10.48%	11
4	Somewhat Agree	10.48%	11
5	Completely Agree	2.86%	3
	Total	100%	105

- Has a lack of health insurance coverage made you consider one of the following?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Has a lack of health insurance coverage made you consider one of the following?	1.00	6.00	3.32	1.40	1.95	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Skip a doctor's appointment	8.57%	9
2	Cancel an appointment with the doctor	18.10%	19
3	Postpone a doctors appointment	36.19%	38
4	Not purchase medicine	19.05%	20
5	Delay treatment	5.71%	6
6	N/A	12.38%	13

|

Total |

100% |

105

- Over the past 2 weeks, how often have you felt nervous, anxious, or on edge?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Over the past 2 weeks, how often have you felt nervous, anxious, or on edge?	1.00	4.00	1.35	0.65	0.42	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Not all	72.38%	76
2	Several days	21.90%	23
3	More days than not	3.81%	4
4	Nearly every day	1.90%	2
	Total	100%	105

- Over the past 2 weeks, how often have you felt down, depressed, or hopeless?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Over the past 2 weeks, how often have you felt down, depressed, or hopeless?	1.00	4.00	1.43	0.73	0.53	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Not all	68.57%	72
2	Several days	22.86%	24
3	More days than not	5.71%	6
4	Nearly every day	2.86%	3
	Total	100%	105

- Over the past 2 weeks, how often have you felt little interest or pleasure in doing things?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Over the past 2 weeks, how often have you felt little interest or pleasure in doing things?	1.00	4.00	1.36	0.66	0.44	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Not all	73.33%	77
2	Several days	18.10%	19
3	More days than not	7.62%	8
4	Nearly every day	0.95%	1
	Total	100%	105

- On average, how many hours per week do/did you work?

On average, how many hours per week do/did you work?

32

40

46

40

40

40

40

40

40

40

40

40

40

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49

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32

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35

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40

5a 8 horas

40

5

40

No tengo trabajo

2 dias el tiempo no deja

20

40

40

40

40

40

50

40

40

45

30

30

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40

40

40

40

0

- During the past FOUR WEEKS, how many complete work days or shifts have you missed due to your burn/chemical injury?

During the past FOUR WEEKS, how many complete work days or shifts have you missed due to your burn/chemical injury?

0

0

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3 a 4

Ninguna

N/A

15

No tengo trabajo ahora

Dos dia cada semana

0

None

0

1

Q

0

0

0

0

0

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0

0

1

0

40

0

0

- How many jobs do you currently have?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	How many jobs do you currently have?	1.00	2.00	1.04	0.19	0.04	103

#	Answer	%	Count
1	1	96.12%	99
2	2-3	3.88%	4
3	more than 4	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	103

- Is there training in sanitation practices for farm workers in their own language?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Is there training in sanitation practices for farm workers in their own language?	1.00	2.00	1.09	0.28	0.08	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Yes	91.43%	96
2	No	8.57%	9
	Total	100%	105

- Is there health and hygiene training of workers in their own language?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Is there health and hygiene training of workers in their own language?	1.00	2.00	1.13	0.34	0.12	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Yes	86.67%	91
2	No	13.33%	14
	Total	100%	105

- What toilet facilities are provided for workers (e.g., pit latrines, portable toilets, flush toilets)?

What toilet facilities are provided for workers (e.g., pit latrines, portable toilets, flush toilets)?

Baños

baño

Baños

baños

Baños

baños

Baños

bathrooms

Bathrooms

baños

40

baños

Baño portátil

Baños portátiles

Portátil

Portatiles

Banos portatiles

Portable toilets

Portable toilets

All

Baños

Baños

Baños

Baños

Baños

Bathroom

Baños

Flush

Everything

Banos portatiles

Everything

Bañod

Baños

Todo

Everything

- Is shade available to you?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Is shade available to you?	1.00	2.00	1.23	0.42	0.18	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Yes	77.14%	81
2	No	22.86%	24
	Total	100%	105

- Have you been exposed to pesticide?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Have you been exposed to pesticide?	1.00	3.00	1.15	0.43	0.19	104

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Yes	87.50%	91
2	No	9.62%	10
3	unsure	2.88%	3
	Total	100%	104

- Have your employers ignored you needing help?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Have your employers ignored you needing help?	1.00	3.00	1.52	0.62	0.38	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Yes	54.29%	57
2	No	39.05%	41
3	Maybe	6.67%	7
	Total	100%	105

- When given this scenario: If I encounter a serious food safety issue such as food poisoning, I can report it to the relevant department in time. Do you agree or disagree?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	When given this scenario: If I encounter a serious food safety issue such as food poisoning, I can report it to the relevant department in time. Do you agree or disagree?	1.00	5.00	3.11	1.01	1.02	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Strongly disagree	1.90%	2
2	Somewhat disagree	33.33%	35
3	Neither agree nor disagree	22.86%	24
4	Somewhat agree	35.24%	37
5	Strongly agree	6.67%	7
	Total	100%	105

- Do you agree or disagree with this statement: I think I have a strong sense of responsibility for food safety?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Do you agree or disagree with this statement: I think I have a strong sense of responsibility for food safety?	1.00	5.00	4.26	0.85	0.72	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Strongly disagree	0.95%	1
2	Somewhat disagree	4.76%	5
3	Neither agree nor disagree	6.67%	7
4	Somewhat agree	42.86%	45
5	Strongly agree	44.76%	47
	Total	100%	105

- When buying food, I try to understand its safety as much as possible by checking the shelf life, color, and taste. agree or disagree

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	When buying food, I try to understand its safety as much as possible by checking the shelf life, color, and taste. agree or disagree	1.00	5.00	4.40	0.85	0.72	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Strongly disagree	0.95%	1
2	Somewhat disagree	3.81%	4
3	Neither agree nor disagree	6.67%	7
4	Somewhat agree	31.43%	33
5	Strongly agree	57.14%	60
	Total	100%	105

- I believe that most of the foods circulating in the market are safe. Agree or Disagree

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	I believe that most of the foods circulating in the market are safe. Agree or Disagree	1.00	5.00	4.22	1.03	1.07	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Strongly disagree	2.86%	3
2	Somewhat disagree	8.57%	9
3	Neither agree nor disagree	1.90%	2
4	Somewhat agree	37.14%	39
5	Strongly agree	49.52%	52
	Total	100%	105

- During the past 30 days, how much money did your family/did you spend at supermarkets or grocery stores?

During the past 30 days, how much money did your family/did you spend at supermarkets or grocery stores?

400

450

200

300

500

500

Baños

200

500

200

400

500

600

0

200

250

550

500

600

700

100

400

500

600

400

500

700

500

400

300

450

500

600

500

700

700

400

600

Baños

680

600

550

250

600

700

550

800

800

500

700

700

600

400

800

900

700

300

500

700

700

600

600

600

600

500

600

700

500

600

500

600

600

500

200

400

500

600

500

350

100

2000

De 1200 a 1500

800

500dls

\$800

Mucho por que yo estoy limitado a todo en estos momentos

300

240

1000

200

500

300

700

500

700

800

1500

250

1000

200

500

1200

1000

400

100

- Was any of this money spent on nonfood items such as cleaning or paper products, pet food, cigarettes or alcoholic beverages?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Was any of this money spent on nonfood items such as cleaning or paper products, pet food, cigarettes or alcoholic beverages?	1.00	3.00	1.62	0.50	0.25	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Yes	39.05%	41
2	No	60.00%	63
3	prefer not to say	0.95%	1
	Total	100%	105

- About how much money was spent on nonfood items?

About how much money was spent on nonfood items?

0

30

0

40

150

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

300

0

200

100

60

200

0

0

0

0

0

0

50

0

0

0

0

0

0

400

50

0

100

0

0

0

0

170

0

300

300

200

0

0

50

90

0

200

60

0

70

90

0

0

50

100

50

100

0

0

0

50

0

50

100

50

0

100

40

150

0

0

0

100

\$500.00 en productos de limpieza

400

0

\$300

200 dolares y eso que hase falta

100

20

800

100

100

50

0

100

50

0

0

100

280

150

100

200

200

250

0

- During the past 30 days, {did your family/did you} spend money on food at stores other than grocery stores?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	During the past 30 days, {did your family/did you} spend money on food at stores other than grocery stores?	1.00	3.00	1.83	0.40	0.16	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Yes	18.10%	19
2	No	80.95%	85
3	prefer not to say	0.95%	1
	Total	100%	105

- During the past 30 days, how much money did your family/did you spend on eating out?

During the past 30 days, how much money did your family/did you spend on eating out?

0

0

0

0

2

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

20

0

0

0

0

0

0

20

0

0

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50

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0

0

30

30

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

60

0

40

0

0

0

0

0

40

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

20

0

0

\$200.00

Ninguna

0

\$200

500 dolares o mas

00

0

200

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

100

0

0

0

100

30

70

150

0

- During the past 30 days, how much money did your family/did you spend on food carried out or delivered?

During the past 30 days, how much money did your family/did you spend on food carried out or delivered?

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

30

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

70

-

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

50

50

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

10

0

0

0

0

0

50

0

20

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

No compro

Ninguna

0

\$200

350 dolares

000

25

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

0

50

0

0

0

50

0

0

0

0

- Do you live or work near heavy traffic, airport, gas station, or idling vehicles?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Do you live or work near heavy traffic, airport, gas station, or idling vehicles?	1.00	2.00	1.30	0.46	0.21	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Yes	70.48%	74
2	No	29.52%	31
3	Prefer not to say	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	105

- Have you been exposed to oils, grease, de-greaser, or fuels?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Have you been exposed to oils, grease, de-greaser, or fuels?	1.00	2.00	1.16	0.37	0.14	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Yes	83.81%	88
2	No	16.19%	17
3	Prefer not to say	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	105

- Do you use pesticides or herbicides inside your home/workplace or outside on grass or garden?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Do you use pesticides or herbicides inside your home/workplace or outside on grass or garden?	1.00	2.00	1.39	0.49	0.24	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Yes	60.95%	64
2	No	39.05%	41
3	Prefer not to say	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	105

- Do you live in or near a dump site or Super Fund site?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Do you live in or near a dump site or Super Fund site?	1.00	2.00	1.70	0.46	0.21	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Yes	29.52%	31
2	No	70.48%	74
3	Prefer not to say	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	105

- Have you had/known chemical injury or major exposure?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Have you had/known chemical injury or major exposure?	1.00	2.00	1.41	0.49	0.24	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Yes	59.05%	62
2	No	40.95%	43
3	Prefer not to say	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	105

- Do you drink water from a well, lake, or rive

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Do you drink water from a well, lake, or rive	1.00	3.00	1.26	0.46	0.21	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Yes	75.24%	79
2	No	23.81%	25
3	Prefer not to say	0.95%	1
	Total	100%	105

- Do you work or live where co-workers/co-inhabitants complain about the air quality or smell

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Do you work or live where co-workers/co-inhabitants complain about the air quality or smell	1.00	2.00	1.31	0.46	0.22	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Yes	68.57%	72
2	No	31.43%	33
3	Prefer not to say	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	105

- Do you carpool to work?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Do you carpool to work?	1.00	2.00	1.18	0.38	0.15	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Yes	81.90%	86
2	No	18.10%	19
3	Prefer not to say	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	105

- Does your home have running water?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Does your home have running water?	1.00	2.00	1.05	0.21	0.05	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Yes	95.24%	100
2	No	4.76%	5
3	Prefer not to say	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	105

- Do you have access to safe drinking water at home/work?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Do you have access to safe drinking water at home/work?	1.00	2.00	1.08	0.27	0.07	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Yes	92.38%	97
2	No	7.62%	8
3	Prefer not to say	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	105

- Do you feel safe when you're at work/home

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Do you feel safe when you're at work/home	1.00	5.00	2.61	1.09	1.19	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Definitely not	11.43%	12
2	Probably not	46.67%	49
3	Might or might not	17.14%	18
4	Probably yes	19.05%	20
5	Definitely yes	5.71%	6
	Total	100%	105

- Have you witnesses to corruption or other irregular practices?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Have you witnesses to corruption or other irregular practices?	1.00	3.00	1.25	0.47	0.22	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Yes	77.14%	81
2	No	20.95%	22
3	I don't know	1.90%	2
4	Prefer not to say	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	105

- Have you been a victim of crime?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Have you been a victim of crime?	1.00	3.00	1.83	0.47	0.22	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Yes	20.95%	22
2	No	75.24%	79
3	I don't know	3.81%	4
4	Prefer not to say	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	105

- Do you believe crime is a problem your neighborhood?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Do you believe crime is a problem your neighborhood?	1.00	5.00	3.28	1.15	1.32	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Definitely not	7.62%	8
2	Probably not	22.86%	24
3	Might or might not	14.29%	15
4	Probably yes	44.76%	47
5	Definitely yes	10.48%	11
	Total	100%	105

- How much do you agree or disagree with the following statement? “I feel safe in the Central Valley”

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	How much do you agree or disagree with the following statement? “I feel safe in the Central Valley”	1.00	5.00	2.51	1.12	1.26	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Strongly disagree	15.24%	16
2	Somewhat disagree	47.62%	50
3	Neither agree nor disagree	13.33%	14
4	Somewhat agree	18.10%	19
5	Strongly agree	5.71%	6
	Total	100%	105

- How much do you agree or disagree with the following statement? "Are the police acting lawful in the exercise of their duties?"

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	How much do you agree or disagree with the following statement? "Are the police acting lawful in the exercise of their duties?"	1.00	5.00	2.22	1.15	1.33	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Strongly disagree	32.38%	34
2	Somewhat disagree	33.33%	35
3	Neither agree nor disagree	20.00%	21
4	Somewhat agree	8.57%	9
5	Strongly agree	5.71%	6
	Total	100%	105

- Does your documentation status affect how safe you feel while working or at home?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Does your documentation status affect how safe you feel while working or at home?	1.00	4.00	1.51	0.63	0.40	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Yes	54.29%	57
2	No	41.90%	44
3	I don't know	1.90%	2
4	Prefer not to say	1.90%	2
	Total	100%	105

- Please select the three (3) issues you think are the greatest problems within your community

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Burglaries/thefts (auto)	1.45%	5
2	Burglaries/thefts (residential)	1.45%	5
3	Child abuse	0.58%	2
4	Child sexual predators/Internet Safety	1.16%	4

5	Disorderly conduct/public intoxication/noise violations	1.74%	6
6	Disorderly youth (e.g., cruising or gathering)	2.61%	9
7	Domestic violence (adult)	11.88%	41
8	Driving under the influence (i.e., alcohol or drugs)	9.28%	32
9	Drug abuse (e.g., manufacturing, sale, or use of illegal/prescription drugs)	18.55%	64
10	Fraud/identity theft	2.61%	9
11	Gang activity	21.74%	75
12	Gun violence	15.65%	54
13	Hate crimes	0.58%	2
14	Homeland security problems	0.29%	1
15	Homeless- or transient-related problems (panhandling)	3.19%	11
16	Homicide	0.29%	1
17	Mugging	0.87%	3
18	Physical assault	1.16%	4
19	Prostitution	0.58%	2
20	School safety (e.g., bullying, fighting, or weapons)	1.45%	5
21	Sexual assault/rape (adult)	0.58%	2
22	Traffic issues/residential speeding	0.29%	1
23	Underage drinking	0.87%	3
24	Vandalism/graffiti	1.16%	4
	Total	100%	345

- To what extent do you trust your law enforcement agency?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	To what extent do you trust your law enforcement agency?	1.00	5.00	1.25	0.70	0.50	104

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Not at all	85.58%	89
2	A little	7.69%	8
3	Somewhat	3.85%	4
4	A lot	1.92%	2
5	To a great extent	0.96%	1
	Total	100%	104

- Community policing involves officers in your law enforcement agency working with the community to address the causes of crime in an effort to reduce the problems themselves through a wide range of activities. Based on this definition, to what extent do you think your law enforcement agency practices community policing?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Community policing involves officers in your law enforcement agency working with the community to address the causes of crime in an effort to reduce the problems themselves through a wide range of activities. Based on this definition, to what extent do you think your law enforcement agency practices community policing?	1.00	5.00	1.36	0.86	0.75	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Not at all	80.95%	85
2	A little	7.62%	8
3	Somewhat	8.57%	9

4	A lot	0.00%	0
5	To a great extent	2.86%	3
	Total	100%	105

- If applicable, please specify your religion.

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	If applicable, please specify your religion.	1.00	2.00	1.03	0.17	0.03	101

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Catholic	97.03%	98
2	Christian	2.97%	3
3	Morman	0.00%	0
4	Hinduism	0.00%	0
5	Islam	0.00%	0
	Total	100%	101

- Agree or disagree that one does not need to practice one’s cultural celebrations.

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Agree or disagree that one does not need to practice one’s cultural celebrations.	1.00	5.00	2.30	1.09	1.18	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Strongly disagree	24.76%	26
2	Somewhat disagree	40.95%	43
3	Neither agree nor disagree	18.10%	19
4	Somewhat agree	12.38%	13
5	Strongly agree	3.81%	4
	Total	100%	105

- Agree or disagree: one must preserve one’s cultural heritage.

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Agree or disagree: one must preserve one’s cultural heritage.	1.00	5.00	3.67	1.05	1.09	103

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Strongly disagree	2.91%	3
2	Somewhat disagree	15.53%	16
3	Neither agree nor disagree	12.62%	13
4	Somewhat agree	49.51%	51
5	Strongly agree	19.42%	20
	Total	100%	103

- Agree or disagree One must be proud of one's cultural group.

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Agree or disagree One must be proud of one's cultural group.	1.00	5.00	3.40	1.16	1.36	104

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Strongly disagree	1.92%	2
2	Somewhat disagree	28.85%	30
3	Neither agree nor disagree	17.31%	18
4	Somewhat agree	30.77%	32
5	Strongly agree	21.15%	22
	Total	100%	104

- Agree or disagree One does not need to trust a higher being.

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Agree or disagree One does not need to trust a higher being.	1.00	5.00	3.14	1.14	1.30	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Strongly disagree	6.67%	7
2	Somewhat disagree	29.52%	31
3	Neither agree nor disagree	16.19%	17
4	Somewhat agree	38.10%	40
5	Strongly agree	9.52%	10
	Total	100%	105

- Agree or disagree "Because of my culture, I would rather see a Curanderos or Curanderas than an a doctor"

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Agree or disagree "Because of my culture, I would rather see a Curanderos or Curanderas than an a doctor"	1.00	5.00	2.59	1.08	1.16	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Strongly disagree	13.33%	14
2	Somewhat disagree	43.81%	46
3	Neither agree nor disagree	16.19%	17
4	Somewhat agree	23.81%	25
5	Strongly agree	2.86%	3
	Total	100%	105

- Agree or Disagree One does not need to always avoid conflict with others.

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Agree or Disagree One does not need to always avoid conflict with others.	1.00	5.00	3.54	1.11	1.24	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Strongly disagree	3.81%	4
2	Somewhat disagree	21.90%	23
3	Neither agree nor disagree	6.67%	7
4	Somewhat agree	51.43%	54
5	Strongly agree	16.19%	17
	Total	100%	105

- Agree or Disagree One should never offend one's elders.

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Agree or Disagree One should never offend one's elders.	1.00	5.00	3.42	1.30	1.69	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Strongly disagree	6.67%	7
2	Somewhat disagree	28.57%	30
3	Neither agree nor disagree	4.76%	5
4	Somewhat agree	36.19%	38
5	Strongly agree	23.81%	25
	Total	100%	105

- Agree or Disagree One's family is the main source of one's identity.

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Agree or Disagree One's family is the main source of one's identity.	1.00	5.00	3.79	1.13	1.27	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Strongly disagree	2.86%	3
2	Somewhat disagree	16.19%	17
3	Neither agree nor disagree	10.48%	11
4	Somewhat agree	40.00%	42
5	Strongly agree	30.48%	32
	Total	100%	105

- Agree or Disagree One's bond with one's cultural group must be very strong.

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Agree or Disagree One's bond with one's cultural group must be very strong.	1.00	5.00	3.96	1.09	1.18	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Strongly disagree	1.90%	2
2	Somewhat disagree	14.29%	15
3	Neither agree nor disagree	6.67%	7
4	Somewhat agree	40.00%	42
5	Strongly agree	37.14%	39
	Total	100%	105

- Agree or Disagree: A woman should sacrifice everything for her family.

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Agree or Disagree: A woman should sacrifice everything for her family.	1.00	5.00	2.80	1.33	1.76	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Strongly disagree	14.29%	15
2	Somewhat disagree	40.95%	43
3	Neither agree nor disagree	11.43%	12
4	Somewhat agree	17.14%	18
5	Strongly agree	16.19%	17
	Total	100%	105

- Agree or Disagree A woman must be a source of strength for her family.

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Agree or Disagree A woman must be a source of strength for her family.	1.00	5.00	3.79	1.06	1.12	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Strongly disagree	2.86%	3
2	Somewhat disagree	12.38%	13
3	Neither agree nor disagree	14.29%	15
4	Somewhat agree	43.81%	46
5	Strongly agree	26.67%	28
	Total	100%	105

- Agree or disagree A man must provide for his family financially.

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Agree or disagree A man must provide for his family financially.	1.00	5.00	3.87	1.10	1.22	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Strongly disagree	0.95%	1
2	Somewhat disagree	17.14%	18
3	Neither agree nor disagree	11.43%	12
4	Somewhat agree	35.24%	37
5	Strongly agree	35.24%	37
	Total	100%	105

- Agree or disagree A woman is considered the backbone of the family.

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Agree or disagree A woman is considered the backbone of the family.	1.00	5.00	3.53	1.19	1.41	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Strongly disagree	3.81%	4
2	Somewhat disagree	22.86%	24
3	Neither agree nor disagree	13.33%	14
4	Somewhat agree	36.19%	38
5	Strongly agree	23.81%	25
	Total	100%	105

- Agree or Disagree In your current workplace, do you feel that men and women are treated equally?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Agree or Disagree In your current workplace, do you feel that men and women are treated equally?	1.00	5.00	3.02	1.17	1.37	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Strongly disagree	7.62%	8
2	Somewhat disagree	35.24%	37
3	Neither agree nor disagree	14.29%	15
4	Somewhat agree	33.33%	35
5	Strongly agree	9.52%	10
	Total	100%	105

- Do you agree or disagree that homosexuality is natural and normal.

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Do you agree or disagree that homosexuality is natural and normal.	1.00	5.00	3.29	1.10	1.21	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Strongly disagree	6.67%	7
2	Somewhat disagree	19.05%	20
3	Neither agree nor disagree	24.76%	26
4	Somewhat agree	38.10%	40
5	Strongly agree	11.43%	12
	Total	100%	105

- Agree or Disagree men hold all of the power in the house

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Agree or Disagree men hold all of the power in the house	1.00	5.00	3.11	1.18	1.40	104

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Strongly disagree	3.85%	4
2	Somewhat disagree	38.46%	40
3	Neither agree nor disagree	16.35%	17
4	Somewhat agree	25.96%	27
5	Strongly agree	15.38%	16
	Total	100%	104

- Agree or Disagree Men and Women are equal in your line of work?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Agree or Disagree Men and Women are equal in your line of work?	1.00	5.00	3.20	1.24	1.53	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Strongly disagree	8.57%	9
2	Somewhat disagree	26.67%	28
3	Neither agree nor disagree	17.14%	18
4	Somewhat agree	31.43%	33
5	Strongly agree	16.19%	17
	Total	100%	105

- Agree or Disagree that women define themselves through their family and children rather than independently or as a couple

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Agree or Disagree that women define themselves through their family and children rather than independently or as a couple	1.00	5.00	3.27	1.14	1.30	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Strongly disagree	2.86%	3
2	Somewhat disagree	31.43%	33
3	Neither agree nor disagree	17.14%	18
4	Somewhat agree	33.33%	35
5	Strongly agree	15.24%	16
	Total	100%	105

- Agree or Disagree Machismo has affected my life

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Agree or Disagree Machismo has affected my life	1.00	5.00	3.81	1.16	1.34	105

#	Answer	%	Count
1	Strongly disagree	6.67%	7
2	Somewhat disagree	10.48%	11
3	Neither agree nor disagree	6.67%	7
4	Somewhat agree	47.62%	50
5	Strongly agree	28.57%	30
	Total	100%	105

REFERENCES

- Airhihenbuwa, C. (1999). Of Culture and Multiverse: Renouncing 'the Universal Truth'. *Journal of Health Education, 30*, 267-273.
- America Counts Staff. (2021, August 25). *California Remained Most Populous State but Growth Slowed Last Decade*. Retrieved from United States Census Bureau: <https://www.census.gov/library/stories/state-by-state/california-population-change-between-census-decade.html>
- AMERICA COUNTS STAFF. (2021, August 25). *California Remained Most Populous State but Growth Slowed Last Decade*. Retrieved from United States Census Bureau: <https://www.census.gov/library/stories/state-by-state/california-population-change-between-census-decade.html>
- Aqtam, I., & Darawwad, M. (2018). Health Promotion Model: An Integrative Literature Review. *Open Journal of Nursing, 8*, 485-503.
- ASSOCIATED PRESS. (2008, July 24). *Record fine in worker's death*. Retrieved from Los Angeles Times : <https://www.latimes.com/archives/la-xpm-2008-jul-24-me-briefs24.s7-story.html>
- Bailey, W. F. (1908). The Story of the Central Pacific. The Rise of the Big Four: Huntington, Stanford, Crocker, and Hopkins. In W. F. Bailey, *The Story of the Central Pacific* (pp. 164-203). Fair Oaks: Bruce C. Cooper Collection.
- BEA. (2023, March 31). *Annual percent change in the real gross domestic product of California in the United States from 2000 to 2022 [Graph]*. Retrieved 2023, from Statista: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/306775/california-gdp-growth/>
- (2015). *BENEFITS OF FARMLAND CONSERVATION IN CALIFORNIA*. California Department of Food and Agriculture .
- Blackford, M. G. (1970). Businessmen and the Regulation of Railroads and Public Utilities in California during the Progressive Era. *Business History Review, 44*(3), 307-319.
- BRIEFING: November 14, 2012 AGENDA ITEM #5*. (2012, November 14). Retrieved from California High-Speed Rail Authority: <https://hsr.ca.gov/programs/green-practices-sustainability/agricultural-conservation-preservation/>
- California Department of Food and Agriculture*. (2021). Retrieved from CALIFORNIA AGRICULTURAL STATISTICS REVIEW: https://www.cdfa.ca.gov/Statistics/PDFs/2020_Ag_Stats_Review.pdf
- California's Central Valley*. (n.d.). Retrieved from USGS: <https://ca.water.usgs.gov/projects/central-valley/about-central-valley.html>
- Colford, P. (2013, April 2). *AP Stylebook*. Retrieved from Associated Press : https://www.apstylebook.com/blog_posts/1
- Cullum Clark, J. H. (2022, May 25). *Quality of life promotes prosperity and opportunity in America's best places to live*. Retrieved from George W. Bush Preidential Center: <https://www.bushcenter.org/publications/quality-of-life-promotes-prosperity-and-opportunity-in-americas-best-places-to-live>
- Curl, C. L., Meierotto, L., & Som Castellano, R. L. (2021). Understanding Challenges to Well-Being among Latina FarmWorkers in Rural Idaho Using in an Interdisciplinary, Mixed-Methods Approach. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 18*(1), 169.

- DEFINING UNDOCUMENTED*. (n.d.). Retrieved from Immigrants Rising : https://immigrantsrising.org/wp-content/uploads/Immigrants-Rising_Defining-Undocumented.pdf
- Dimitri, C., Effland, A., & Conklin, N. (2005). *The 20th Century Transformation of U.S. Agriculture and Farm Policy*. United States Department of Agriculture. Economic Reserach Service. (2022). *Farm finance indicators, state ranking, 2020*. U.S. Department of Agriculture.
- Economic Reserach Service. (2022). *Government payments by program*. US Department of Agriculture .
- Elkind, E. N., Hecht, S., & Horowitz, C. (2013). *A High Speed Foundation How to Build a Better California Around High Speed Rail*.
- ERA Economics LLC. (2020). *Economic Impacts of the COVID-19 Pandemic on California Agriculture*. California Farm Bureau Federation UnitedAg. ERA Economics.
- Evidence-based Practice Center Systematic Review P. (2014). *Project Title: Improving Cultural Competence to Reduce Health Disparities for Priority Populations*. Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality.
- FACT SHEET WHY SAVE FARMLAND?* (n.d.).
- Garcés, I. C., Scarinci, I. C., & Harrison, L. (2006, April 25). An examination of sociocultural factors associated with health and health care seeking among latina immigrants. *Journal of Immigrant and Minority Health*, 8, 377–385.
- Gleeson, S. (2010). Labor Rights for All? The Role of Undocumented Immigrant Status for Worker Claims Making. *Law & Social Inquiry*, 35(5), 561-602.
- Heizer, R. F. (1940). Aboriginal use of bitumen by the California Indians, in Geologic formations and economic development of the oil and gas fields of California: State Division of Mines, Bull. 118. In S. F. Hodgson, *California Indians, Artisans of Oil* (p. 74).
- Hilton, A. (1986, April 13). Analysis of Pender's Health-Promotion Behavior Model. *Canadian Journal of Nursing Resreach*, 18(1), 57-66.
- Iwelunmor, J., Newsome, V., & Airhihenbuwa, C. O. (2014, Febuary). Framing the impact of culture on health: a systematic review of the PEN-3 cultural model and its application in public health research and interventions. *Ethcity & Health*, 19(1), 20-46.
- Johnston, W., & McCalla, A. (n.d.). *California Agriculture in the 21st Century*. University of California Agriculture and Natural Resources Communication Services: Giannini Foundation of Agricultural Economics.
- Karpman, J. (2021). *Brace for Impact: The Environmental and Economic Effects of Shifting Passenger Travel from Airplanes to High-Speed Rail*. UCLA Luskin Center for Innovation, Luskin School of Public Affairs. Los Angeles, CA: The University of California Institute of Transportation Studies.
- Keough, G. (2021). *Giants Fans Can Find Solace in California, U.S. Agriculture's MVP in Sales*. U.S. DEPARTMENT OF AGRICULTURE.
- Khokha, S. (2008, June 6). *Teen Farmworker's Heat Death Sparks Outcry*. Retrieved from NPR: <https://www.npr.org/2008/06/06/91240378/teen-farmworkers-heat-death-sparks-outcry>
- KITROEF, N., & MOHAN, G. (2017). *Wages rise on California farms. Americans still don't want the job Trump's immigration crackdown is supposed to help U.S. citizens. For California farmers, it's worsening a desperate labor shortage*. Stockton: Los Angeles Times.

- Larsen, K. S., Krumov, K., Van Le, H., Ommundsen, R., & Veer, K. (2007). Threat Perception and Attitudes Toward Documented and Undocumented Immigrants in the United States: Framing the Debate and Conflict Resolution. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 7(4).
- Lee, B.-A., & Oh, D.-J. (2013). The effects of health perception on living health belief, living satisfaction and wellbeing-oriented activities according to swimming participation with middle-aged women. *Journal of Exercise Rehabilitation*, 9(3), 381-388.
- Linder, M. (1987). Farm Workers and the Fair Labor Standards Act: Racial Discrimination in the New Deal. *Texas LAW REVIEW*, 65, 1335-1387.
- Lopez, A. (2014). *The State of Farmworkers in California*. Retrieved from Center for Farmworker Families: <https://farmworkerfamily.org/information>
- Lowell, D. L. (1985). THE CALIFORNIA SOUTHERN RAILROAD AND THE GROWTH OF SAN DIEGO PART I. *The Journal of San Diego History*, 31(4).
- Luna, G. T. (1998). AN INFINITE DISTANCE?: AGRICULTURAL EXCEPTIONALISM AND AGRICULTURAL LABOR. *U. PA. JOURNAL OF LABOR AND EMPLOYMENT LAW*, 1(2), 487-510.
- Marcia, J. E. (1993). The Ego Identity Status Approching to Ego Identity. In J. E. Marcia, A. S. Waterman, D. R. Matteson, S. L. Archer, & J. L. Orlofsky, *Ego Identity: A Handbook for Psychosocial Research* (pp. 3-21). New York: Springer New York.
- Martin, P., Hooker, B., Akhtar, M., & Stockton, M. (2016, August 23). Research Article How many workers are employed in California agriculture? *California Agriculture*, 71(1), 30-34.
- Maslow, A. A. (1955). *Theory of Human Motivation*. New York .
- Mayer, G., Collins, B., & Bradley, D. H. (2013). *The Fair Labor Standards Act (FLSA): An Overview*. Congressional Reserach Service.
- Mines, R. (2006). *Data on Crops, Employment and Farmworker Demographics: A Resource for California Rural Legal Assistance* . UC Davis.
- Moser, D. (n.d.). *Determining Quality of Life*. Retrieved from Cardiology Advisor: <https://www.thecardiologyadvisor.com/home/decision-support-in-medicine/cardiology/determining-quality-of-life/>
- National Institute for Occupational Safety . (2021, September 21). *AGRICULTURAL SAFETY*. Retrieved from Center for Disease Control and Prevention: <https://www.cdc.gov/niosh/topics/aginjury/default.html>
- Newel, G. (2017, March 11). *HEALTH EQUITY AND CALIFORNIA'S CENTRAL VALLEY* . Retrieved from www.communitymedical.org/CMC/media/Mobile-Docs/2017/Health-Equity-and-California-Central-V alley-Gail-Newel-MD-MPH-FACOG.pdf
- Nixon, H., Holian, M., Niles, J., & Pogodzinski, J. M. (2018). *Measuring the Economic Impact of High Speed Rail Construction for California and the Central Valley Region*. San José State University, College of Business. San José, CA: Mineta Transportation Institute.
- North, D. M. (2018). *California at War: The State and the People During World War I*. University Press of Kansas.
- Paddison, J. (2005). *1866-1920: Rapid Population Growth, Large-Scale Agriculture, and Integration into the United States*. Retrieved from Calisphere: <https://calisphere.org/exhibitions/essay/5/population-growth/>
- Proto, E., & Rustichini, A. (2013, November). A Reassessment of the Relationship between GDP and Life Satisfaction. *PLoS ONE*, 8(11), 1-10.

- Purdum, T. S. (2000, September 6). *NATIONAL ORIGINS: CALIFORNIA'S CENTRAL VALLEY; Where the Mountains Are Almonds*. Retrieved from The New York Times : <https://www.nytimes.com/2000/09/06/dining/national-origins-california-s-central-valley-where-the-mountains-are-almonds.html>
- Puskorius, S. (2015, February). The Methodology of Calculation the Quality of Life Index. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 5(2), 156-159.
- Raingruber, B. (2017). Health Promotion Theories. In B. Raingruber, *Contemporary Health Promotion in Nursing Practice*. Jones & Bartlett Learning, LLC.
- Rogers, P., & Buttice, Ph.D, M. K. (2013, October). *Farmworkers in California: A Brief Introduction*. Retrieved from CRB Short Subjects : <https://latinocaucus.legislature.ca.gov/sites/latinocaucus.legislature.ca.gov/files/CRB%20Report%20on%20Farmworkers%20in%20CA%20S-13-017.pdf>
- Rosales, O. A. (2012). *Mississippi west": Race, politics, and civil rights in california's central valley, 1947–1984* . Retrieved from roQuest Dissertations & Theses Global: The Humanities and Social Sciences Collection: <https://search-proquest-com.lib-proxy.fullerton.edu/docview/1102291107?accountid=9840>
- Rose, J. (2021, April 19). *Immigration Agencies Ordered Not To Use Term 'Illegal Alien' Under New Biden Policy*. Retrieved from NPR: <https://www.npr.org/2021/04/19/988789487/immigration-agencies-ordered-not-to-use-term-illegal-alien-under-new-biden-polic>
- Rosenstock, I. (1974). Hisotorical orgins of the Health Belief Model. *Health Education Monographs*(2), 328-343.
- Runyan, J. L. (n.d.). *Federal Laws and Regulations Affecting Farm Safety*. Washington D.C.: Food and Rural Economics Division Economic Research Service U.S. Department of Agriculture.
- Sanders, S. (1998). Perspective: Statewide farmland protection is fragmented, limited. *California Agriculture*, 52(3), 5-11.
- Thompson, Jr., E. (2009). *Agricultural Land Loss & Conservation*. American Farmland Trus. U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services. (n.d.). *Legal Immigration*. Retrieved from Center for Immigration Studies: <https://cis.org/Immigration-Topic/Legal-Immigration>
- United States Census Bureau. (2012). *American Community Survey 2009-2011 Public Use Microdata*.
- Vranich, J., & Cox, W. (2013). *California High Speed Rail: An Updated Due Diligence Report*. Due Diligence Report.
- Wang, T. (2004). Concept analysis of functional status. *International journal of nursing studies*, 41(4), 457–462.
- Weinstein, J. N., Geller, A., & Negussie, Y. (2017). *Communities in Action: Pathways to Health Equity*. Washington D.C.: The National Academies of Sciences Engineering and Medicine.
- Williams, J. I., & Wood-Dauphinee, S. (1989). Assessing Quality of Life: Measures and Utility. In F. Mosteller, & J. Falotico-Taylor, *Quality of Life and Technology Assessment: Monograph of the Council on Health Care Technology*. Washington, D.C.: Institute of Medicine (US) Council on Health Care Technology.
- Worster, D. (1979). *Dust Bowl: The Southern Plains in the 1930s*. Oxford University Press. Retrieved from Oxford University Press.

Yen, I. (2020, June 30). *COVID-19 and California's Central Valley*. Retrieved from Massachusetts Institute of Technology: <https://livingwage.mit.edu/articles/67-covid-19-and-california-s-central-valley>